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Testing of Kitemill's Airborne Wind Energy System at Lista, Norway. Assessing the impacts on birds. A pilot study.

Arnold Håland

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Front page: Migrating Greyleg Goose *Anser* at Lista, Southern Norway. 5. september 2018. Photo: A. Håland.

FOREWORD

Different technology and methods for producing renewable energy are developing globally. A new technology under test is the capture of high winds for energy production using an airborne wind energy system (AWES). In Norway, pioneering work has been done for several years on testing a new prototype, Kitemill, under the auspices of the company Kitemill AS. The test area is located at Lista Airport, Farsund municipality in Agder, Southern Norway. After applying for permission to continue testing in spring 2018, Farsund municipality adopted a permit that allowed for continued testing for a 2 year period. One of the conditions behind the permit was a need of knowledge of possible effects of flying kites on the natural environment, and more specifically, the effects on birds (Farsund municipality 2018). On the basis of a recognized need for new knowledge, therefore, an order was issued from Farsund municipality to Kitemill AS that a monitoring plan had to be prepared. Early April 2018, NNI Resources AS (NNI), was contacted by Kitemill AS and given the task of drawing up a monitoring plan adapted to the testing of Kitemill on Lista. A plan for a pilot study was soon after accepted and project activities initiated.

The goal of a scientific approach to the question of possible adverse effects of AWES on birds is to gain experience of the bird's response to the testing/operation activity of the Kitemill altitude wind system. Empirical field data and evaluation of how birds responds behaviourally to a high-wind energy production system, would set a basis for assessing impacts and consequences for both breeding and migratory birds, and further, provide a basis for mitigating measures connected to operation of AWES plants.

Lista, located near the southern tip of Norway, has long been known for its rich bird life and its location as a key site along the Norwegian and Nordic bird migratory flyway. Every year, over 200 species of birds are observed in the Lista area, i.e. the potential for interaction with a AWES plant is present. An important ecological perspective is that bird species appear at Lista at different times of the year, i.e. as both nesting birds, and migratory and wintering birds. Furthermore, birds are found in different numbers throughout the year, in different local natural environments and with varying flight behaviour. During spring and autumn passages, there is a great deal of variation in migratory activity, in relation to time of day (many species migrate mainly at night), and not least in relation to different weather conditions (wind direction, wind force, rainfall and temperature). The complexity of bird migration associated with a large numbers of factors induce a need of focus on different approaches in terms of exposure to the high wind system and the associated risks when operating the kites. Regarding research on impacts of AWES on birds, this is not a unique situation, the same questions are central regarding studies of possible negative impacts of conventional wind power plants. Established knowledge from research on wind power is therefore an important basis when it comes to building new knowledge about impacts from AWES such as Kitemills (and other types of high-wind installations (cf. European Commission 2016)

Being a pilot project, and having available only 9 days for fieldwork at the Kitemill operation site, a selection was made regarding key issues connected to the main question: do AWES plants affect birds negatively? With an approved project plan, the field work related to the test area and the testing of the Kitemill started in mid and late June 2018, focusing on nesting birds. The field work was completed at the beginning of September 2018, focusing on migratory birds during the middle of autumn migration.

Since its launch in June, research activities has been conducted on the main and associated themes, as well as analyses of field data from the test area at Lista Airport. A draft of the report was finalized at the beginning of November 2018 and finished in December 2018. Planning, fieldwork, data analyses and reporting have been carried out by avian ecologist Arnold Håland (Cand. real.), head of NNI.

NNI would like to thank Kitemill AS for the assignment and good cooperation during the project period in 2018. Team Kitemill on Lista always showed up and gave good information about test flights and conditions related to the Kitemill project. Furthermore, Thomas Hårklau and Lode Carnel assisted with a lot of good information throughout the project period, and Jon Gjerde for valuable feedback on a draft report. Thanks to everyone!

Bergen, Norway
December 20, 2018.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Globally, much work is being done regarding the development of new technologies for the production of renewable energy, from further development of known technologies related to hydropower, wind power, solar power, earth energy, bioenergy and more. The goal is to phase out to a sufficient extent the fossil-based, non-renewable energy from coal, oil and gas. With international agreements in place, especially the Paris Agreement (2015), the focus on new technology and new solutions has gained even greater political and societal impetus during the last years.

The utilization of wind for the production of energy (and electricity) has gained a large and global position in what is called a "green shift". Wind turbines with large (and increasingly larger) turbines are increasingly being built around the world, while new, innovative solutions are being sought. A new technology under development is Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWES), i.e. energy technology that harvest medium and high altitude wind resources. Kitemill AS is a Norwegian company that has come a long way in developing new solutions during the last decade. In its application for continued testing on Lista, Kitemill writes: "Kitemill is one of approximately 30 companies globally that are working to develop the next generation of wind power technology. By using the dragon principle to extract wind power, one can now reach new wind resources that previously have not been possible to extract. The wind increases in strength and stability the higher up from the surface one gets. Therefore, high altitude wind turbines will produce more full hours than normal wind power at most geographical locations globally. In addition, the principle allows one to handle the same produced power as a conventional wind turbine with less than 10% of material use. Lista is one of the sites in the world with the highest mean winds. In addition, the wind quality is very smooth and good, providing good guidance when trying out new wind power technology. Testing of the high wind technology required many engineers from different stages of the world, and it is difficult to coordinate when in addition to take care of weather conditions. The wind conditions on Lista make it much easier to plan such testing. In addition to wind conditions, Farsund Airport Lista has good infrastructure for testing. It is a combination of cultivated land and concrete pavement that makes it easy to place equipment for testing. Furthermore, the area is outside controlled airspace, which makes it possible to operate without involving the air traffic tests. With reference to the Civil Aviation Authority, there is one advantage when headwind operation in controlled airspace will presuppose that the air traffic tests coordinate the operation".

Following a decision in Farsund municipality on March 27, 2018, as a regulatory authority, a monitoring plan related to effects on birds shall be prepared, a response of the application from Kitemill AS to continue their test operation at Lisat Airport. Farsund Municipality writes in its decision: "Conditions are set for a monitoring plan to be drawn up to control how a bird responds during testing operations. The plan must be approved by the municipality. Further: " As far as the municipality understands on the initiative holder, on a global scale, limited research has been done on the impact of high wind energy production in relation to birds. In cases where the basis of experience is limited and the level of conflict is unclear, a monitoring program during a test period will be important to better clarify the level of conflict. Testing and research should then also be possible during the periods of the year when there is greater density of birds in the area. "

When it comes to Kitemill's suggestion that there is little impact-related research related to altitude wind installations, this seems correct, although some general issues have been discussed in several studies (e.g. Khan & Rehan 2016). Lack of knowledge of effects and environmental consequences is also pointed out by European Commission (2016), in its document on challenges related to the commercialization of AWES facilities. They state that there are no empirical studies at all, which imply that the NNI project is the first to be carried out. Otherwise, a great deal of research has been conducted related to traditional wind power (see overview in Rydell et al. 2017), and thus much knowledge can be transferred to studies on how altitude wind systems can affect birds and bird populations. Research related to how birds collide with other human devices, such as glass windows, power lines, buildings, aircraft, cars, lighthouses, TV towers, various communications facilities/towers, is also an important perspective regarding new research on AWES (Ferrer et al. 1999, Lucas et al. 2007, Day et al. 2015, van Doren et al. 2017), not least when assessing combined influences and overall mortality in bird populations. The large global reduction in populations of birds and animals (WWF's The Living Planet Report (2018), shows the seriousness we face when it comes to how physical elements and human activities affect bird behavior, increase their mortality and reduce populations. This is why research-based knowledge is essential to make the right decisions and implement the best mitigation measures when new technologies is used.

In relation to whether a high wind energy system (AWES) can have a negative impact on birds, there are some key issues that need to be clarified. First, it is the occurrence of birds in and around test areas/operation sites that is important and is a key factor in a risk model, i.e. occurrences where both species and number of birds are important. Without birds no risk. Although over 200 species of bird are observed in the Lista area annually, and often in large numbers, there is a great deal of variation in terms of 1) bird numbers, 2) habitat use, 3) diurnal and nocturnal activity, 4) flight behavior, 5) flight altitude (the latter is particularly relevant for AWES operations), and 6) differences in activity in relation to weather conditions (not least for migrating birds during spring and autumn; i.e. wind direction, wind strength, rainfall and temperature). Secondly, it is important to clarify how birds in the action/test area respond to the test activity (here specific Kitemill test flights). Birds can react with i) avoidance of the entire test area, ii) avoidance in flight in the vicinity of the test facility (here line and kite - see description of the Kitemill concept later in the report), and iii) collisions with/contact with line and kite can occur. In wind turbines, collision frequency (number of collisions/turbine/year) is a key parameter in risk assessments (cf. Rydell et al. 2017), although avoidance behaviour has turned to be a key issue regarding risk assessments i relation to conventional wind power establishments.

Even with a limited amount of field work at Lista in 2018, the project has illuminated a number of relevant issues, with results which in turn are linked to various research disciplines. That said, it is also important to note the existence of a bird observatory on Lista, which through monitoring activities harvest a large amount of bird-data each year, data available through the online database at Artsdatabanken (Artskart). Much of the available data also results from reports from birdwatchers, both local and guests at Lista. For relevant and important species, excerpts from the database have been made as an perspective for own observations from the 2018 fieldwork. A credit therefore goes to the eager and dedicated bird observers at Lista, both local and visiting persons.

Implementation of the project work, which is targeted in the approved monitoring plan (see Håland 2018), has been carried out by zoologist/avian ecologist Cand. real. Arnold Håland (AH), NNI, Bergen. AH has extensive research experience (15 years) from the University of Bergen, Norway (UiB - Department of Zoology; Department of zoo-ecology), as well as conducting a large number of professional studies and R&D projects in the field under the auspices of the NNI (in the period 1995 - pt). The Kitemill project on Lista is therefore carried out with a broad research background regarding the many questions related to and possibly how AWES operations can affect birds in an undesirable direction. As the report will show, a number of questions have been answered, but new ones have been added, an experience that can be recognized in all research fields. From a scientific perspective, similar research, about effects of AWES on biodiversity and birds, is not known to have been carried out elsewhere. As such, the pilot project at Lista in 2018 has been a valuable exercise, but with a limited scope in relation to the many variables that may influence local conditions, the behaviour and number of birds and those possible interactions with an aerial wind energy system like Kitemill's kite turbine solutions.

2 THE KITE TURBINE KITEMILL

2.1 Kitemill – technology and function

The Kitemill concept is designed and constructed to be able to harvest wind power at various greater heights (compared to a traditional windpower plant). Kitemill consists of a dragon/wing and line and it is this that generates power via traction/lifting power (cf. Fig. 1). Furthermore, a ground system is included which converts the traction to electricity. To operate/run the system is an important part of the control system that controls both the winch, the rope and the dragon (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Principle model for a kite turbine. Source: Kitemill AS.

The Kitemill system (Fig. 1), like other altitude wind systems, can operate at various selected heights, related to the fact that wind speed and stability increase with height (Fig. 2). Available wind power increases with the cube (X 3) of increased wind speed, for example an increase from 5 m/s at 100 meters to 11 m/s at 1000 meters height gives an increase in available power from 80 W/m² to the entire 580 W/m² (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Principle model for a kite turbine. Source: Kitemill AS.

2.2 Running and testing the kite turbine

During test production/operation of the plant, the line is pulled out of the winch (see Fig. 1) and out to the desired line length for take-off. In case of adequate wind, the kite is then released, which is then pulled/flyes to the desired height. Furthermore, the kite is run in a loop/spiral (Fig. 3a), thereby creating a large traction force which is converted to electricity in the ground system (Fig. 1). When the test run/production is completed, the kite is withdrawn to the starting point (Fig. 3b, c).

Fig. 3. Visualization of the operational phases of take off/production and return of the kite. Source: Kitemill AS.

Fig. 4. During operation/production phase in the Kitemill system, the kite run in a spiral (see also Fig. 3), or for the individual spiral - in a circle. Source: Kitemill AS.

Fig. 5. Mobile kite ready for test flying, seen here from east to west in the Lista test area at site P1. September 6, 2018. Photo: A. Håland.

3 TEST AREA LISTA, SOUTHERN NORWAY

3.1 Localization

Lista is located at the southern coast of Norway, in Farsund municipality, Agder county, with the open landscape exposed to the North Sea (Fig. 6). Lista Airport is centrally located in the outer landscape of Lista Country (Fig. 7), and mainly surrounded by farmland (Fig. 8).

Fig. 6. Location of Lista, Farsund municipality, on the outer coast of Vest Agder, Norway.

Fig. 7. The airport at Lista is centrally located on the outer Lista, with the main runways oriented NW-SE. The AWES test area is located inside the airport (red). The Lista airport is closed regarding aviation business.

Fig. 8. Lista airport is mainly surrounded by farmland with a distance of 1.3 km to the marine environment/sea at Listastrendene (here measured from the main runway to the beach in the North Hassel Bay). The test area used by Kitemill during the years, and in 2018, is bounded by red. Source: Norgebilder.no.

3.2 The test site at Lista airport

Tests of the Kitemill high altitude wind energy system, areas inside the Lista airport have been used (Fig. 9). The same section of the airport area has been used over time (since start of testing - see overview of numbers of test flights in Tab. 1). Different wind conditions, directions and strength, make it necessary to use different locations for testing the kite. When laying the line from the turbine and the kite at horizontal initiation, the length is about 400 meters when using the mobile unit (Fig. 5), but up to 1000 meters when using a fixed pilot plant (cf. Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Test area at Lista airport. Red cross indicates location for today's fixed pilot plant (30kW). Green dots indicate the most used locations for the mobile test unit. Yellow surfaces show the typical flight zones associated with different wind directions. Displayed flight zones are approximately 400 meters in length. A test site/area is used based on the prevailing wind direction. Map: Kitemill AS.

4 TEST ACTIVITY AT LISTA

4.1 Test activity 2015 to 2018 – number of days

Kitemill started with development work and tests in 2008, with an increase in test activity in 2013 to 2014. Since 2015, monthly test activity has been at Lista, but weather conditions are always a key factor, which over time has meant that some test sessions were not completed. An overview of completed tests over the last 4 years (2015 - 2018) is shown in Tab. 1. The largest activity in 2018 has been in the period April-May 2018, with test flights at 10 different days (Tab. 1). The activity has been relatively similar for the last 3 years.

Tab. 1. Overview of Kitemill test activities at Lista during 2015 - 2018, shown as number of days of completed test flights. NNI monitored several test sessions in June and September 2018. Data: Kitemill AS

Month	2015	2016	2017	2018
January	0	3	0	0
February	0	2	1	2
March	0	2	1	4
April	1	3	0	3
May	0	1	2	7
June	4	5	1	2
July	0	0	1	0
August	0	3	5	0
September	2	2	5	2
October	2	0	0	0
November	0	0	3	1
December	0	0	1	?
<i>Total</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>20</i>

4.2 Test activity regarding time of day

In the case of Kitemill test flights in 2018 (Fig. 10), they have been conducted at different times of the day, but nearly all the tests have been conducted during the day and with most tests between 1100 and 1900 (Fig. 10). No tests have been done during the night, and only a few tests conducted before 9:00 in the morning (May 30, 2018 only). Factors that have controlled the test flights are logistics in relation to the innovation work, where many different elements of the system are involved, but testing also requires satisfactory wind conditions (preferably 6 m/s or more - info Kitemill AS). In the periods of own my field work i 2018, wind conditions were the controlling factor for which days test flights were conducted (also discussed later in the report). A key part of the project in 2018 has been to gain insight into if and how birds responded to the test flights and related activities. Field work during test flights was conducted both in June and September 2018 (Tab. 1), where test flights were closely monitored on June 26 and September 6, 2018. Details of the layout and methodology of the fieldwork are given in a later chapter.

Fig. 10. Distribution of test activity in 2018, i.e. test flights in relation to time of day. N=55. Data: Kitemill AS.

Fig. 11. Kitemill's team after completed test flight on September 6th, 2018. Photo: A. Håland.

5 FIELDWORK AT LISTA 2018

5.1 Schedule and fieldstudies in 2018

In order to establish a firm basis for assessing possible negative effects of the Kitemill test flying with the turbine kit, field work was set up in the test area and surrounding landscape, aimed at documentation of both nesting birds and migratory birds, including monitoring of test activities in both periods, all according to plan (cf. Håland 2018). Field studies during 3 day-periods were made in 2018, a total of 9 days at Lista. The program was carried out according to plan, but due to minor shifts in the test activities (which are among other things dependent on logistics and weather), the first field session was postponed from May to June. An overview of field days in the 3 periods is given in Tab. 2. Travel activity to and from Lista is kept outside (regarding time used). On a daily basis, the daily fieldwork comprises a minimum of 8 hours, but for several days the fieldwork was continuous from morning to evening (0400 to 2200), interrupted only by short breaks. Total field time in the test area, in the surrounding influence areas at the airfield and in the larger Lista landscape, is approximately 110 hours.

Tab. 2. Overview of completed fieldwork for 3 periods in 2018, and with information on areas and key issues (see also text).

Period	Date	Test flights	Test area	Surrounding area	Main issue
I	14.6	No	Yes	Yes	Breeding birds
I	15.6	No	Yes	Yes	Breeding birds
I	16.6	No	Yes	Yes	Breeding birds
II	25.6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Breeding birds
II	26.6	No	Yes	Yes	Breeding birds
II	27.6	No	Yes	Yes	Breeding birds
III	4.9	No	Yes	Yes	Migratory birds
III	5.9	No	Yes	Yes	Migratory birds
III	6.9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Migratory birds

5.2 Birds in the test and influence area

Regarding how human activities effect biodiversity, here birds, impact areas are usually 2-divided: 1) the area of action itself and 2) the area of influence, i.e. a geographical zone in the surrounding area at/around the area of action. In this project, the action area is bounded inside Lista Airport (cf. Fig. 9), defined as the area of test activities for Kitemill, while the surrounding Lista landscape is an larger influencia area (Fig. 9). Areas of influence are in general a dynamic area, ie it is not a given geographic area, but the area where a defined organism (here bird species) is really impacted. Birds' large mobility imply that birds in the wider Lista landscape in a short space of time can be within the test area itself, especially this applies to species with large home ranges, and not least, birds during migration (and winter). Based on this, observations and mapping were made especially in the zone around Lista airport. In an assessment of the effects of high-wind systems such as Kitemill, data of birds in a larger landscape is also important information, compared with observations in the test area itself and in the nearby influence area (cf. Fig. 9). For a more detailed discussion of field methodology, cf. next chapter.

5.3 Methods for mapping and observing birds

The occurrence of birds in a given area (here primarily the test area and the near-influence area) is the first key factor in assessing negative impact / risk assessments from new measures / activities, here Kitemill's high-wind facility. However, birds are mobile, with mobility and area use associated with phases in the annual cycle (migratory, nesting and wintering periods). The schedule in 2018 focused on both nesting time (June) and pulling time (September), a scheme that requires the use of different field methods. The methods are standardized and well-tested over many 10-years, but still require adaptation to local conditions and problematics such as must be answered. However, high wind systems, such as Kitemill, are something new/a new activity, as there is no research on the effects on birds. Influencing airspaces up to 400-500 meters in height (and perhaps higher in the long term), they require a special focus on the bird species that use this airspace in different parts of the annual cycle in large, and more detailed, relative to phases in nesting time, time. on the clock and in relation to prevailing weather conditions. The following is a brief description of the methodology used in the project in 2018 and the approach to important issues in the project.

5.3.1 Occurance of birds during the breeding season

Surveying of birds during the breeding season in June was carried out by several methods: 1) point census and 2) zone observations. Point census was used during June (breeding birds), with points distributed in the test area and the near influence area (cf. Fig. 12). In June, the song activity is somewhat limited for the species that breed early in the spring, but adequate for those that breed later. The point census in the test area showed which birds were active during the test flight period. In the case of point census, a standard 5-minute observation period is used, where all birds seen and heard are registered at the point. Results are shown as the total number observed for all 10 points (covering most of the test area), number of each species, number of pr. point (relative density), as well as species per point (a measure of local species richness). Then author has experience with the method from decades of fieldwork. About 85 of the observations in the forest are bird song and other vocalizations; in open landscape to a greater extent direct observations (but in the test area itself, the singing activity of Skylark and Meadow pipits was central as there was little of other species).

Field activity aimed at the surrounding area was aimed at observing birds' use of the cultural landscape and forests that surround the test area, both inside and outside the Lista airport. In principle, important bird areas in the influence area can generate bird activities towards and in the test area (cf. Håland 2018). In the Lista landscape it is relevant to focus on important wetland areas such as the Slevdalsvannet and Hellemyra, but also important areas further afield can initially be thought of as recruiting birds into the nest area during the breeding season (Listastrendene, lakes in the SE, seabird colonies (for example Rauna with focus on Lesser black-backed gulls in June). Mobility and use of open air space is an important issue regarding breeding gulls (here: the risk zone with regard to Kitemill flights), but also other species such as Cranes and harriers. How the airspace is used varies between species, with much impact of the weather conditions (for example swallows, swifts, birds of prey and seagulls) and time of day (song activity is greatest during and after sunrise, as well as most migratory birds migrate at night during the spring and autumn migration).

Zonal observations is based on a given observation point where a surrounding, bounded area is covered. In an open cultural landscape (and other open natural environments), which is important on Lista, such a zone can be relatively large. In the report (see also species list in Appendix 1) the term outer landscape is used for the area outside the test and influence area. In mid-June, a

number of such zones were surveyed and birds registered.

The possibility of species determination do vary with the observation distance. Large species such as Hen herrier, Cranes and Greyleg goose, were observed and determined at up to 1 - 2 km distances (mainly binoculars 10x50 were used). For smaller species (mainly passerines), the effective observation zone is consistently smaller, but OK up to 200 - 300 meters (occasionally larger, slightly dependent on species). Bird song (and other vocalizations) are important elements during censuses (see point census methods), but influence the size of the mapped area. Zone observation was also used for mapping birds' use of the test area during periods both with and without test flights. Clarifying whether there are local movement corridors in and around the test area was an important approach in the project (local movement routes, cf. Håland 2008, 2016), however, this is less likely in an open landscape such as Lista. More fragmented occurrence of distinct ecosystems (such as wetlands), can influence local movements. In the monitoring plan (cf. Håland 2018), this was a focused issue due to many bird rich wetlands at Lista. Zone observation was also used in the influence area and in the outer landscape, with the main focus on clarifying whether there were occurrences and activities of birds in a surrounding landscape that could be recruited to the test area and thereby enter a risk zone.

5.3.2 Autumn migration in September

As Lista is located at a key point in the coastal migratory routes in Norway, a large number of bird species may occur in large concentrations. Then, knowledge of the migratory birds' occurrences, activity and migratory behavior is an important aspect in relation to the risk of negative interactions with a AWES, here Kitemill's test activity. A monitoring period was therefore added to the field program, timed to the beginning of September. This is a period that can usually have significant activity of migratory birds (cf. also discussions of bird migration in general and about interannual variations in the extent and dynamics of the migration). The bird migration on Lista has been studied since the 1950s, first by English ornithologists (Griffin et al. 1956), in the more recent 10-year more systematic studies associated with Lista Bird Station (Wold et al. 2017). However, there are no studies from what is here the test area at the Lista airport, but there are a good many *ad hoc* observations from all seasons (see next chapter). Such observations are useful but not sufficient for the assessments that are central to the main questions in the project. During the migration periods, exemplified by the fieldwork at the beginning of September 2018, counting of migratory birds in the test area was done from fixed points, ie NV in the test area, or in the east, from points P1 and P2 (see Fig. 12). The migratory activity varied a lot from day to day, guided by prevailing weather conditions. Weather data was therefore obtained from the Meteorological Inst (www.met.no).

5.3.3 Observation of birds during test flights with Kitemill

A key issue in the project with respect to require knowledge how birds responded to the Kitemill test flights, ie to the flying kite and lines (see Fig. 1, 2 and 3), close observations of birds and their behaviour were done. Scan sampling, but also focal animal (cf. Altmann (1974)), was used, with the observer located with a good overview of the test area and surrounding landscape. Observational aspects was: i) birds' avoidance of the test area, based on observation of birds in a surrounding zone, for example, up to 500 meters from the test facility; (ii) birds' avoidance of the actual high-wind system (line/kite), so-called "micro-avoidance" (Everaert 2014), i.e. birds that clearly change course and possible height, and iii) collision with the Kitemill elements (which may cause injury or death). Collision frequency (measured as number of injured or dead birds per unit

of time), is a key parameter when discussing effects of conventional wind turbines on bird and bird populations (Rydell et al. 2017).

Fig. 12. Test and influence area at Lista airport. The area bounded by red is defined in the bird monitoring project 2018 as the *test area* (or *action area*). Dashed line indicates an area called the *influence zone* in the report. All areas outside this are just the *outer landscape*. Locations of the point census areas (in June - 10 points) is shown with black dots. Morning monitoring of migratory birds (September), was mainly done from 2 sites, P1 and P2 (yellow stars). Map: Kitemill AS.

5.4 Use of ad hoc observations

Birdwatchers in Norway have shown increasing activity in Norway in recent decades. With access to easy registration of observations in the Species Database (artsdatbanken – Artsobservasjoner), the volume of bird observations has increased significantly since the opening of this service in 2007. Older field data is also increasingly being entered into database, all available there or in the Artskart. The amount of observational data varies widely between geographical locations and landscape sections, bird-rich areas naturally have greater field activity and thereby more bird sightings. Although much of the reported data is not based on standardized and systematic methodology, a large volume of observations over time will be a useful source of data when considering the function and significance of local areas, for example in relation to new interventions or new human activities. Lista has long been known as a bird-rich and important bird area in Norway, both due to its location in the coastal flyway, but also offering varied and rich habitats for an range of birds species. Local and visiting birdwatchers have therefore, over time, reported a wide range of bird observations, data that it is free to use when relevant for issues to be

investigated/answered. In Artskart there are per October 31, 2018, a total of 1,256 million observations from the Lista landscape. Birds observed are not far from Kitemill's test area at Lista Airport (Figs. 2 and 9), so the use of data from Artskart is therefore highly relevant.

However, the use of such data must be carefully evaluated against the issues to be answered, but with the important perspective that reported birds are completely independent of specific measures that are being considered in this project. It is also natural to evaluate available data against own field data and observations of birds' behavior and use of the test area and the surrounding area. Evaluation in this report is based on a demarcation of the test area (action area), a surrounding area of influence, and birds' use of open air space (considering single species or species groups), available observational data were then extracted, analysed and presented in the report in relation to specific questions asked. Relevant groups that are more closely assessed are birds of prey and waders ("meadow birds"), species associated with open cultural land at Lista Airport. When it comes to bird occurrences in specific important areas, for example Listastrendene and Slevdalsvann, bird reports are available (Wold et al. 2012, Olsen 2014).

5.5 Natural conditions at the test site

Different habitats and ecosystems house different bird species throughout the breeding season, with distinct bird communities and distribution of species in terms of occurrence, density, and their proportion in the bird community. The test area at Lista Airport (Fig. 12) is primarily a larger, open cultural landscape, dominated by grassland where local farmers are currently producing grass for cattle and sheep. Agriculture activities are experienced throughout the airport area where grassland predominates. Integrated into this landscape are also the airport's facilities, where runways and taxiways are important elements that also influences the local occurrences of birds (acts as a distinct habitat with particular use of several bird species – see below). The test site for the Kitemill test flights also includes shrub and forest which have a different bird fauna in contrast to the open landscape (located in the north and east of the test site). In the transition between the open agricultural area and the forest there are varied edge zones (ecotones) to which several bird species are associated. Together, this provides varied habitats for birds, cf. the delimitation of the test site (Fig. 12). In the outskirts of the test area there are also several wetlands and marshes, environments which have their particular breeding bird species (especially *Hellemyra* in the NØ, also described in a nature databases – Naturbase (cf. Håland 2018)). In the outskirts of the testing area, and in the surrounding outer landscape, there is also species with a potential risk with regard to negative effects, including some seabird species that periodically exploit resources in the farmland (for example several gull species). This landscape also was surveyed during both periods in June 2018 (a total of 6 field days in June).

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Monitoring of the Kitemill's test activity was not specified in detail regarding the local authority (Farsund Municipality 2018), but they wanted an assessment if and how the Kitemill test activities effected birds at Lisata. The project plan and field protocol NNI proposed (cf. Håland 2018), later approved in spring 2018, but had to be adjusted somewhat along the way. As no research has been conducted on AWES regarding effects on birds and bird populations, the fieldwork at Lista was focused on some key questions, but also with a perspective to a wider set of issues. The initial (and logic) question is whether the use of the high-wind energy systems has negative and undesirable effects on local birds and local bird populations, but also if AWES have negative impacts on migratory birds. Globally many AWES are in a testing phase regarding new solutions and new technologies, and many with elements similar to the Kitemill concept. Providing answers to such questions requires different methodological approaches because: 1) birds issues involve a large number of species with different ecology and different habitat use; 2) species occurs at different times throughout the year, i.e. as breeding birds, birds migrating during spring and autumn seasons, and also as overwintering birds; 3) the species behave with great differences in terms of numbers (common species and rare species) and 4) the species behaves differently, use different habitats and often differ in response to human activities, all aspects influencing the risk of being exposed to negative effects of the flights with a AWES system (such at the Kitemill). Finally, 5) weather conditions are a very important factor regarding bird activity, behavior and area use (including use of airspace). With this perspective, the field work was aimed both at breeding birds in the local test area on Lista, but also focus on migrating/resting birds during the autumn migration (cf. Håland 2018). In the following, the main issues regarding breeding birds in the test area at Lista (Fig. 12), are first discussed, with the aim of clarifying which species could be in a risk zone for undesirable effects, but also a more holistic view of birds in the surrounding landscape at Lista. During the fieldwork in June, a full day of test activity with Kitemill was also monitored (June 25th – Tab. 2).

Regarding the autumn migration, 3 days in September (4th. -6th.) was used for logging relevant field data. Results from this field session is discussed in the subsequent chapters, including the complexity of migration dynamic and behavioural response to weather conditions and time of the day. Risks of adverse impacts from AWES are closely integrated with the occurrence/quantity of birds and their migratory behavior in the test area, as well as there was expected a close link to prevailing weather conditions, with wind direction, wind strength, rainfall and temperature setting important premisses for the migrating birds. During fieldwork in September, several test flights were monitored on September 5th, focusing on the bird's response to the turbine kite, including observations of bird numbers and activity before, during and after the test flights. Initially in the next chapter, a brief description of the natural conditions in and around the test area, is also given.

6.1 Birds in the test area and surrounding the open landscape

If not very many, there are some species that are specifically related to the open farmland. They are often referred to as *meadow birds* or *farmland birds*. Species and densities of each species are governed by a number of factors, where the use of farmlands (intensive vs. extensive operation) is a key factor, but also the size of the area, the distribution between dry and wet fields, and patchy occurrences of shrubs and trees, have great significance for which species occur and the overall bird community (Håland 2016). The field data from Lista in June 2018 showed that especially two

species occurred frequently and were evenly widespread in the test area and the near-influence area, and they are therefore at Lista considered as two key species regarding risk assessments; it is the Skylark *Aluda arvensis* and the Meadow Pipit *Anthus pratensis*. Within surveyed sections at Lista Airport, both species can be considered common and habitat characteristic species. The point census made in June documented well the occurrences of both of these species associated with the open landscape, the same also apply to Swift *Apus apus* and Barn Swallow *Hirundo rustica* (Fig. 13), which frequently hunted insects above the open fields. In a management context, the Skylark is nationally Red-listed (VU - vulnerable), while the Meadow Pipits are not (however so in many EU-countries). Thus, in an international perspective, Norway has an important role in managing the population of Meadow Pipits (listed as a «species of responsibility» in Norway). Therefore, how these two species are affected by the testing activity with Kitemill is of national interest (see further discussion below). In addition to Skylarks and Meadow Pipits, Starlings *Sturnus vulgaris* (red listed - NT) was observed in small flocks in the farmland area, but to a lesser extent in the test area itself (not observed at the point census in June - see Fig. 13). The maximum was a flock of Starlings of 32 birds on June 15th, observed just east of the test area, in grasslands both inside and outside the Lista airport. The Starlings is probably nesting on buildings in the surrounding

Fig. 13. Result of the point census in the Kitemill test area, which includes both open farmlands, edge zones and forest areas. Results given by numbers for each species. In total: 128 birds recorded. Species marked with blue are those that to the greatest extent use the local air space, especially Barn Swallow and Swifts under their foraging trips. Further Skylark and Meadow Pipit with song flights over open fields and Siskin and Common Redpolls with their frequent song flights over both forest and open land. Census period: morning June 26, 2018.

areas of Lista, or in boxes placed out by humans (naturally in hollow trees, but larger, hollow trees probably have little occurrence in the Lista area). Other species that could be found in the open cultural landscape are shorebirds such as Lapwings *V. vanellus* and Curlew *N. arquata* (both nationally listed as EN - threatened and VU - vulnerable)). Both species is nationally in great decline, a trend that is also well documented for the Lista area (Olsen 2014). However, none of these species were detected in the test area or nearby surroundings in June 2018 (6 observation days), but a few Curlews were observed further to the east of the test area, and also in the south toward Nordhassel (also heard during the point censuses). Another shorebirds, the Redshank *Tringa totanus* (currently not Red-listed), was heard several times from the wetland area SØ of the main runway, and also from Hellemyra, but this species was not detected within the test area itself (Fig. 12). The population of Redshanks is also in great decline in the wetlands of southern Norway, ie occurrences during the breeding season are of significant interest. In the meadow birds that are strongly associated with moist cultural fields, the hot and dry summer during 2018 may have affected local occurrences, but as mentioned above, especially Lapwings and Curlew have had a rapid and large decline on Lista over the past 10 years (Olsen 2014). A total absence of lapwings may also be affected by timing of the fieldwork; the species nest early and leave early from its breeding grounds (perhaps especially during dry summers).

Another group of species that is strongly associated with the open airspace are Barn Swallows and Swift (Fig. 13). In the test area, Swifts were frequently observed (Fig. 13), as several pairs, among others, were nesting on nearby aircraft hangars. Individuals or small groups (up to 8-10 ind.) were therefore regularly observed throughout both fieldwork periods in June. Likewise, Barn Swallow, often seen in various air strata throughout the breeding season (and also in September during the migration). With a specific use of the airspace, from just above ground level to greater heights (hundreds to several 1000 meters), Swallows and Swifts are basically a risk group of birds in relation to testing/operation of high altitude wind systems (AWES) such as Kitemill (cf. further discussion in the chapter on risk assessment). Among other observed species, which also fall into the category of particularly interesting management species, is the Marsh Harrier *Circus aeruginosus* (nationally red-listed - VU). The Marsh Harrier has a small breeding population in Norway and with Lista as one of the classic breeding areas in the country. The species breeds more or less permanently in Slevdalsvatnet, in the border area SV of the Lista airport (Olsen 2014). Marsh harriers were not observed within the actual test area in June, but was seen several times during field work, especially over western parts of the airport (towards/at Slevdalsvatnet), but they were also seen hunting east across the meadows south of the airport (including in the Nord-Hassel area). Birds of prey, such as harriers hawk and other raptor species, are considered among the risk species when it comes to collision with conventional wind turbines (Rydell 2017). Raptors are therefore a species group that must also be considered vulnerable with regard to high wind energy systems. Another, but not a red-listed species, the Crane *Grus grus* is nesting with one or more pairs in the Lista area (Olsen 2014). The species was heard several times in June (from the area in the west nearby Slevdalsvatn), and observed in the test area in September (see below). The cranes belong, like eagles, falcons, harriers and hawks, to a category of birds that may initially considered to be subject to collision with the kite line during testing and operations.

In addition to breeding species associated with the open cultural landscape, and species related to the airspace above (birds of prey, swifts, swallows), there was another feature of the test area at Lista Airport and in the open fields around the airport. During the fieldwork in June, there were occasionally large numbers of Lesser Black-backed Gull *Larus fuscus termedius*, probably recruited from the breeding colony on Rauna (primarily), an island located on the coast just south of the

Listastrends. The gulls' use of the area is discussed in more detail in a separate chapter (see below). Another seabird species that nest on Rauna is the Cormorant (subspecies *P. c. sinensis*). Cormorants were seen daily flying over Lista Airport (and a couple of times over the eastern part of the test area), in a route from SØ towards NV (and return). However, the frequency was low, about 1 cormorant per hour of field observation. The movement was largely at a height of about 80 - 100 meters, and was clearly oriented towards NV and the SE. A single cormorant was observed just above the test area, heading south, in the same elevation layer (June 15th). The cormorants hunt fish both in marine environments and in fresh water (especially the *sinensis* cormorants hunt a lot in fresh water, perhaps most autumn, winter (when open water) and during spring – own observations), so the flights across Lista are probably mostly used for daily movements to good fishing sites, but as mentioned above, the frequency was generally low (and always a straight line) and mainly north and east of the test area. The risk level for negative interaction is therefore considered to be low for local Cormorants.

6.2 Birds associated with forest and bush habitats

Many bird species are associated with varied natural environments at the airport and surroundings (pasture, forest edges, houses and other buildings) or with farmland in the border zone around the airport, for example Magpie, Hooded Crow, Jackdaws, wagtails, House Sparrow and Tree Sparrow were observed in the more developed landscape in Northwest (the local "business area"). Occasionally, several of these species were also seen out in the more open farmland or during movement in and near the test area, but generally they flew at low altitude (below 30 meters), and overall with few observations in the test area itself.

In and near the test area together, the bush and the forests constitute a relatively large proportion, in terms of area, but the testing of Kitemills itself is carried out in the open landscape (cf. Fig. 12). In the more closed habitats there was a wide variety of breeding species, associated with either the edge zones or the forest nature itself (Fig. 13). In the edge zones there are species such as Common Whitethroat *Sylvia communis* and Whinchat *Saxicola rubetra*, but in general with low density. Associated forest and forest edges held many common bird species, such as woodpeckers, Wren, Robin, Blackcap, Garden Warbler, Chiffchaff, Willow Warbler, Pied Flycatcher, Blackbird, Fieldfare, Chaffinch, Greenfinch, Lesser Redpoll, Siskin, Linnet and Yellow Bunting. A representative picture of the local bird community at the test site is given in the overall result from the point census (Fig. 13). Forest-associated species spend most of the time in the forest environment itself, being active on the ground or in trees, or at the edges of the forest, ie they have a low risk regarding negative impacts from the testing with AWES. These species are generally infrequently seen in the open landscape, except for species such as Woodpigeon and Fieldfare that nest in trees, but find much of the food in forest openings or in open farmland. However, both species were few and infrequently seen during the field work in June 2018. The forest species generally use the open air space little, but some species, such as Tree Pipits, have song flight from the tree tops (but not very high – normally 30 to 40 meters). The Siskins and Redpolls also spend a lot of time with song flights, but also they are seen relatively low in the air space (below 50 meters). Overall, forest species are therefore considered to be in a low risk group versus the test activity with Kitemill (but also see the section on migratory Passerines). One group, birds of prey, can be an exception, even if they nest in forests. They can hunt in the open countryside, and some-times thermal flights can be an important activity. However, in June 2018 (6 days), few sightings of birds of prey (only Peregrine Falcon - (and Marsh Harrier - see above)) were made, in line with a *ad hoc* observation data (cf. observational data from Artskart – discussed later in the report). However,

variation in flight activity in terms of time of year is an important element for raptors, such as territorial activity in early spring. The risk level for unwanted conflict with AWES test flights can therefore vary for a given bird of prey during the nesting season, but at present there is no knowledge available which species of birds of prey do breed at Lista in addition to the Marsh harrier (Sparrow hawk is a good candidate, however). The frequency of nesting birds of prey is more likely to increase in the hilly landscape to the north, and possible birds from such remote nesting areas can visit the pen landscape at Lista while hunting.

6.3 Focused bird species

In the perspective of the distinctive features of high-wind installations, species which hunt and feed in the open airspace are important species regarding assessing negative exposures and risk of injury/death. Based on the field work in June 2018, a limited number of breeding species have been focused, based on the local occurrence, their behavior and risk of negative impacts from the test activities with the Kitemill energy system. Other bird species observed in the test area (see above and species list in Appendix 1), are either associated with 1) forests and show little use of airspace during breeding season, 2) the use of the test area is infrequent (often rare and uncommon species) or 3) species which in general have low flight heights. Such species are not discussed further in the report. In Tab. 3 is shown species which, based on their use of the test area (and nearby landscape) and their flight behavior, are in principle in a higher risk category than the many forest or forest edge species. In relation to the occurrence/use of the test area and nearby areas of influence, available observation data from online database Artskart has also been included in assessments of several species of the focused species. In particular, the spatial distribution of observations at Lista over time says something about the species' movements and use of different habitats. The flight time from localities in the surrounding area (outer landscape at Lista) to the test area itself is short, i.e. in principle, birds in observed areas outside the limited test area can quickly find themselves in a risk zone where test flights is taking place. Species-specific behavior, specialized habitat selection and use of the test area are thus important for assessing the potential/risk of conflicts with the Kitemill high wind energy system. Documentation on birds 'specific area use (occurrence in different zones), coupled with knowledge of the species' ecology and type of flight behavior, is therefore the way to clarify and evaluate the key issues in the project. Other species may be relevant during the migration periods spring and autumn (see discussion of results from the September fieldwork).

Tab. 3. Based on fieldwork during 6 days in June 2018, the following breeding species at Lista have been assessed as risk species with regard to possible negative effects from test flights with Kitemill (see also text).

Art	Status	Key habitats	Use of space	At test site
Marsh Herrier	Few	Wetland and open fields	Daily – hunting	Few
Crane	Few	Wetland, framland, forests	Daily – movements	Few
Lesser B-b Gull	Common	Farmland	In periods	Many - in periods
Swift	Common	Over farmland, forest, wetlands	Daily – always	Common
Barn Swallow	Common	Over farmland, forest, wetlands	Daily – nearly always	Common
Skylark	Common	Farmland	Song flights - often	Common
Meadow Pipit	Common	Farmland	Song flights - often	Common

6.3.1 Marsh Harrier *Circus aeruginosus*

Birds of prey are generally subject to collisions with various man-made facilities, such as conventional wind turbines (Rydell 2017). At Lista the Marsh Harrier is a well-known breeding species, as one of the relatively few locations in Norway. However, the number of breeding pairs at Lista is small, only 1 to 2 pairs (Olsen 2014). Marsh Harriers have one of its core areas in lake Slevdalsvann, located SV of the airport. The Marsh Harrier was observed 8 times from the test area in June, but always seen to the west, south or east of the test area (moving or hunting birds). On June 14th one harrier was seen along the border of the test area (to the east - probably it came from Hellemyra). In a wider perspective the locations of all reported sightings in the breeding season (April – July) is shown (Fig. 14). For the whole year there are 4345 sightings of Marsh Harriers (Tab. 4), of which 2744 are observations from the period April to July (Tab. 4, Fig. 14). Within the airport area itself, the observations are overall fewer, but the observed pattern are in line with my own observations from June 2018 (during my 6 days of fieldwork). Earlier observations in test area include 46 observations, of which 35 birds was seen in Hellemyra wetland area (a part of the influence area) and 11 observations from Lista airport itself (exact locations not known). There are no observations in Artskart from the test area and near surroundings in 2018, which is probably due to a lack of field activity from local observers.

Tab. 4. Distribution of records of Marsh Harrier at Lista in relation to month. Source: Artskart.

Month	Number of observations
January	0
February	3
March	12
April	775
Mai	1203
June	321
July	445
August	1047
September	503
October	32
November	4
December	0
Year	4345

If we look at the corridor from lake Slevdalsvann and eastwards (south of the airport - see Fig. 14), there are a total of 1384 sightings of Marsh Harriers within this corridor, i.e. about 50% of all sightings reported (period April - July) are from this limited area. The fact that this corridor is important for the Marsh Harrier on Lista is supported by the fact that nearly all my own observations (except one) in 2018 were from this part of the Lista landscape. However, the distribution of the observations in Artskart is much controlled by where local observers place their field activities, for example to the important wetland area Slevdalsvann (which has a total of 1211 observations in the boundary of the wetland area (28%)). The well known nesting area in Slevdalsvatnet (cf. Olsen 2014), will naturally be a core area within their home range during the breeding period, but the relative use of the rest of the home range at Lista is more uncertain. The northern parts of the Lista airport area have few observations (none in June 2018), but there are many observations from Hellemyra wetland, NE of the test area. However, the spatial distribution

of the observations (Fig. 14) shows where the Marsh Harrier can appear over time, however, without the relative importance of individual sites used. When it comes to using the airspace, the Marsh Harrier generally hunts relatively low over wetlands and fields, mostly below 50 meters in height (own observations). For assessment of other birds of prey using the Lista landscape, see discussions in another chapter in the report.

Fig. 14. Plot of observations of Marsh Harrier at Lista in the months of April to July. $N = 2744$. The nesting area in Slevdalsvann (1211 observations recorded) near the western part of the airport, is bounded in a red circle. Important movement corridor in June 2018 is shown (red arrows), based on observations made from the Kitemill test area (orange - see also Fig. 12). Source: Artskart.

6.3.2 Crane *Grus grus*

If we look at the Crane in the same period (April to July – data from Artskart), the picture is much the same as for Marsh Harrier, i.e. Cranes are observed in most of the Lista landscape. Overall, there are 3606 observations, of which 2509 are from the period April to July. 1063 observations are from lake Slevdalsvann, where the species also nest (Olsen 2014). The observations are mainly from the last 10 years. Within the defined area of influence for Kitemill, there are 118 observations, 17 of which are within the Lista airport and in the test area itself (Fig. 12). The rest of the observations are from Hellemyra wetland which borders the test area to the northeast. Cranes were heard from the Slevdalsvann area in June, but the only concrete observation was on the evening of September 4th, when 5 Cranes flew through the test area (towards VNV - see Fig. 15). The breeding population of Cranes at Lista is increasing, with several new pairs being located in recent years (Olsen 2014). The species is also in good progress in Norway as a whole, i.e. the use of the Lista can be expected to increase in the future.

Fig. 15. Cranes passed through the test area on the September 4th; in picture 3 of the 5 birds that passed by almost simultaneously in that evening (20:16 - local time). Photo: A. Håland.

Fig. 16. Plot of observations of cranes at Lista during the period April to July. N = 2509. The Kitemill test area is marked in red. Source: Artskart.

6.3.3 Lesser Black-backed Gull *Larus fuscus intermedius*

Seagulls are known to be at risk when it comes to collisions with traditional wind turbines (Rydell et al. 2017). Gulls use the airspace extensively, both over sea and land. Several gull species feed in the open farmland, an activity which also happens at Lista. During the first field session in mid-June (June 14-16), Lesser Black-backed Gull was the dominant species in the area, in terms of numbers, using many gras fields at The Lista Airport, including several fields in the test area itself. The seagulls were either feeding, and then specifically linked to the farmer's fertilization of the open fields, or they roosted in large flocks. Larger and smaller flocks were observed in many places on June 14th, flocks ranging from some 10s to over 600 individuals as a maximum (in a farmland located along the local road east of the Lista Airport). However, the number diminished rapidly over

the next few days, and on June 16th, gulls was hardly seen in the area. Such dynamic use of farmland is typical of several gull species (own observations). The breeding population at Lista is mainly located on island Rauna, with currently over 4000 breeding pairs (Fylkesmannen i Vest Agder 2015). The colony is the largest one in Norway. The recruitment basis for grazing gulls at Lista is therefore large. Most of the movements on June 14th went to and from the airport area (and to surrounding fields), which movements usually ranged in 50 - 100 meters altitude. The picture was different on June 16th, when only a few gulls were seen, i.e. several 10's of LB-b gulls, observed at about 400 - 500 meters altitude, all in a thermal flight a short distance to the east of the airport (this was on a hot day with little wind). Such thermal flying is relatively common in seagulls under the right weather conditions (in quiet and warm weather). The seagulls' flight behavior and use of the farmland is therefore an important element with regard to risk assessments versus the Kitemill testing activity (see also later in the report). In addition to the Lesser B-b gulls, there was also a small proportion of Herring gull *L. argentatus* (up to 10 ind.). Other gull species were only observed in the surrounding area of the Lista airport, including at Borlaug (some nesting Common Gull *L. canus* – a red-listed (NT) species) and a few Great Black-backed Gulls *L. marinus* at the coast. Lesser Black-backed Gulls is currently the most important gull species regarding risk assessments, but the use of the open farmland is dynamic and primarily related to times of fertilization and mowing (a common behavior seen in several gull species). An open question is how gulls use the farmland outside the breeding season (to a very small extent gulls were observed during the my early September fieldwork).

Fig. 17. Plot of observations of Swifts at Lista during the period of April to July. N = 2896. The Kitemill test site is bounded in red. Source: Artskart.

6.3.4 Swift *Apus apus*

From the Kitemill test area there are only 15 observations of Swifts, as compared to the entire Lista with 2986 observations (Fig. 17). Only 3 observations have been reported from the airport part of the test area, the rest are from the nearby wetland Hellemyra. No observations are from the last 3 years (source: Artskart). However, the Swift uses the entire test and influence area (own

data from 2018), but the use of habitats, and not least the different altitudes in the airspace, varies much over time and especially with local weather conditions. If it is quiet (or low wind) the Swift chases insects in higher air layers, and if it is really quiet and warm, the Swift can hunt in much higher air layers (i.e. at several thousand meters height). On days of wind, the Swifts observed at Lista hunted consistently low, especially over wetlands and wooded areas (own observations in June 2018). Being the most aerial of all birds, swifts are candidates of being negatively impacted by AWES operations.

6.3.5 Barn Swallow *Hirundo rustica*

Similar variation in the use of the airspace can be found in the swallows, for example Barn Swallows that were common in Lista area, for example on the point census (Fig. 13). Barn Swallows were seen daily throughout most of the Lista landscape, but nesting Barn Swallows generally stay local, in contrast to the Swift who can make long journeys in search of insects and other prey (Alerstam 1982). Locally 2 - 3 pairs of Barn Swallows nested in the actual test area in 2018, with nests in an old bunker in the eastern part of the test area (also a nesting site for Whitethroats). In relation to the use of the high-wind energy system, knowledge about the overall use of the airspace in relation to weather and wind conditions is important when impact assessment regarding swallows and martins is done. During periods of strong wind swallows usually hunt low over fields and forests, or over wetlands and water; in quieter and warmer weather, the Barn Swallows usually hunt in the higher air strata, frequently up to a few hundred meters in height. As for the Swift, therefore, the Barn Swallow use the test space for Kitemill when there is little wind, i.e. when test flights have not been completed (see further discussion under risk of negative interaction with the Kitemill operations).

6.3.6 Skylark *Alceda arvensis* and Meadow Pipit *Anthus pratensis*

Both species have a characteristic feature of the use of song flights in the open landscape, so also on Lista, and in the test area. Along with Swift and Barn Swallows (see above), and on some days also Lesser Black-backed Gulls, Skylarks and Meadow Pipits were the most observed in the open parts of the test area (see above also for forest related species – Fig. 13). Skylarks is perhaps the species with the most frequent use of the air, with its song flight up 40 to 100 meters altitude. Song flights of individual birds can last up to 15 minutes, continuously in the airspace. Density of Skylarks was fairly good in the Kitemill test area and the surrounding farmland, regularly 3 to 5 simultaneous singing males were heard from a given observation point. The Skylarks were also the species most observed during the point census throughout the test area (Fig. 13). The Meadow Pipit appear to breed somewhat less dense, but the species has a variable song activity and is not easy to census accurately. Song flight is generally lower in the air, up to 30 - 40 meters is common (own observations in the test area in June 2018). Spending much time in song flights, both species are considered to be at risk for AWES operations (see also discussions later in the report).

6.4 Birds of prey at the Lista Airport

Birds of prey are in general considered risk species in relation to conventional wind power (Rydell et al. 2017). My own field work in June and September 2018 resulted in observations of 8 species of birds of prey, a relatively high number assessed based on a limited field programme (see appendix 1). Marsh Harriers is discussed in a separate chapter. In order to view my own observations into a bigger picture, available data from Artskart were extracted and analysed. Data is taken from a confined area similar to the Lista Airport, i.e. observations recorded at locations *Lista Flyplass*, *Lista*

Flyplass øst and *Hovedkryss Lista Flyplass*. Data from these locations are analysed together. In addition, the area Hellemyra, located just at the east of the airport, is analysed. Birds of prey located/observed in this and nearby areas are only a short flight away from the Kitemill test area, i.e. the use by birds of prey observed of this area is highly relevant in an evaluation of use and risk assessments. It could be argued that all observations from the whole of the Lista landscape could be used in the analysis, but the material from the airport area and Hellemyra is sufficient to answer key questions asked. Local information (on request) just pointed out that the area on and near the airfield was well known as an important area for birds of prey. The extent of sightings is probably also linked to the fact that birds of prey are also an attractive group to look for birdwatchers. In total, analysed data includes 1504 observations of 20 raptor species, distributed on 976 independent observations (Tab. 5). Most species have been detected in and near Hellemyra (20 species), while 16 different species have been registered within the rest of airport area (see Tab. 5). Most of the observations are from the last 10-15 years, but some data are from the 1990s and the end of the 1980s are also included (all observations of birds of prey from the selected areas on the Lista are included). However, the bulk of the records is from 2007 and later. The results of this analysis is therefore considered to be well representative of the current situation regarding the occurrence of birds of prey at Lista.

Tab. 5. Observations of birds of prey at Lista Airport, as well as from nearby Hellemyra wetland area, shown as the number of records and number of birds seen. Maximum number is also shown. Species which breed in Norway are shown in bold. Data source: Artkart.

Species	Airport				Hellemyra				Total	Total	Frequency (%)
	Records	Numbers	Max	Date max	Records	Numbers	Max	Date max	records	numbers	
White-tailed Eagle	5	6	2	13.01.2017	19	20	2		24	26	2,46
Osprey	0	0			3	3	1		3	3	0,31
Golden Eagle	0	0			1	1	1		1	1	0,10
Red Kite	3	3	1		8	8	1		11	11	1,13
Black Kite	6	6	1		6	6	1		12	12	1,23
Marsh Harrier	26	30	3	14.05.2009	70	88	5	30.08.2015	96	118	9,84
Hen Harrier	34	43	3	07.09.2014	92	120	8	07.09.2008	126	163	12,91
Montagu's Harrier	0	0			11	11	1		11	11	1,13
Pallid Harrier	2	2	1		9	9	1		11	11	1,13
Rough-legged Buzzard	7	16	10	16.09.1994	55	63	5	08.10.2011	62	79	6,35
Common Buzzard	47	49	3	30.01.2001	138	278	15	06.09.2010	185	327	18,95
Honey Buzzard	3	3	1		8	9	2		11	12	1,13
Sparrow Hawk	35	63	6	07.09.2008	74	200	25	14.09.2014	109	263	11,17
Goshawk	8	8	1		30	31	2		38	39	3,89
Kestrel	21	45	7	07.09.2008	60	137	20	14.09.2008	81	182	8,30
Red-footed Falcon	2	2	1		2	2	1		4	4	0,41
Hobby	0	0			5	7	3	06.09.2003	5	7	0,51
Peregrine Falcon	46	56			62	82	4	14.09.2008	108	138	11,07
Merlin	17	28	6	14.09.2013	57	65	3	07.09.2008	74	93	7,58
Gyr Falcon	1	1			3	3	1		4	4	0,41
In total	263	361			713	1143			976	1504	1,00

Frequency distribution of species based on observations (Tab. 5) is shown in Fig. 18. The highest frequency is of Common Buzzard, followed by Hen Harrier, Sparrow Hawk, Peregrine Falcon and Marsh Harrier. The results are considered representative, based on the fact that all birds of prey are day-active and have similar discoverability. The distribution between the species will otherwise vary throughout the year, but most maximum numbers have been recorded in the autumn (except for Marsh Harriers (most in May – do breed in the area), and Common Buzzard (in January), also in the airport area. This analysis shows that a fairly large number of birds of prey use Lista over time, i.e. overall Lista is a species-rich area regarding birds of prey. If we dissolve the data in terms of abundance in a short period of time, for example on a daily basis, the picture is that there are usually few birds of prey in the area, except on the best days during migration seasons. If we look at Hellemyra wetland, the maximum number of birds of prey (all species) is, from the same day, September 14th 2008, with 25 Sparrow Hawks, 20 Kestrels and 4 Peregrine Falcons respectively (Tab. 5). Probably on this day migratory birds of prey were recorded for some lengthy time, which at a given locality can produce a greater number of birds of prey on a single day, but optimal migratory conditions may aggregate reports prepared to cross over to Denmark (see map appendix 2). Only a complete and well structured observation program over the whole season can give the full picture regarding density and abundance of the individual species of birds of prey at Lista (this applies to all bird species). Own observations at the beginning of September 2018 (which showed 8 species of birds of prey in one day), support a conclusion that this landscape section at Lista is important for the group of birds of prey, and thus in the risk category regarding impacts from a AWES in operation.

Fig. 18. Frequency distribution (%) of different birds of prey observed in the Lista airport area and in/near Hellemyra. N = 976 (see Table 5). Data source: Artskart.

Fig. 19. Merlin during a break in the hunt at location P2 September 4th. 2018. Merlins are frequently seen in the Lista area during migration. Foto: A. Håland.

6.5 Migratory birds in September

Migratory movements can be observed almost throughout the year, with spring migration having its peak in the period March-May, while the autumn migration last long, from the end of July to mid November. Some species both start and end their migratory activity outside the main migration seasons. In this project, a field period was selected at the beginning of September, a time during the migratory season which imply a number of species. Many species, especially many passerines and waders, migrate to a large extent earlier in the season, while other species have their main migration later in the autumn. Bird migration, with respect to the dynamics in numbers over time, is well documented in many studies. Field work in early September is therefore far from comprehensive in relation to the full bird migration, but the purpose was to get data related to the test flight with Kitemill towards a set of migratory species. A presentation and discussion of occurrences of birds in the Kitemill test area (and the surrounding area), is given in the following chapters.

6.5.1 Variation in weather conditions during migration

The first week of September 2018 was chosen for fieldwork regarding autumn migration, based on Kitemill's planned test flights. In relation to prevailing weather conditions, this was a random choice, but changes in the weather illustrated well the variation that exists when migrants' occurrence and behavior are to be studied and documented (see the next chapters). Actual weather conditions, such as wind force, wind direction, rainfall and temperature, are shown in Tab. 6 for the field period in September (and for the day before and after that). The weather changed much over this short field period (Tab. 6). On September 4th the wind was reversed from the previous day with a new direction from NV (changed from 82 to 280 degrees), but with low wind force, no rain and a good visibility. The conditions were evidently good for migrating passerine birds that day, as a steady move of birds over the test area was recorded during the morning session (observed from sunrise to around noon). At 11:00 the movement of birds was markedly reduced. Number of passing birds was fairly stable over time during the morning, but not with

large numbers of birds. Most common species were Meadow Pipit, White Wagtail and Barn Swallow (see details below). In the time period 07:00 to 09:00, all migratory birds were logged in detail in terms of migration direction, altitude and number of individuals, this to give a quantitative picture of how the migration progressed through the Kitemill test area. The results is shown in Figs. 20 - 22, and Tab. 7, for the three species mentioned. In total, 23 species were observed during this observation period, but most species occurred with a small number, briefly discussed below (see also Appendix 2 for an overall overview of all observed bird species).

Tab. 6. Weather parameters for the perioden September 3 – 7, 2018. Data from Lista weather station. Source: Met.no.

Date	Wind direction – degrees	Wind – middle wind (m/s)	Percipitation (mm)	Temperature	Visualbility (i meters)
3. sept	82	5,9	0	15,6	5000
4. sept	280	3,0	0	15,9	5500
5. sept	325	3,1	0,3	14,7	2500
6. sept	106	7,5	5,2	16,3	3000
7. sept	95	13,5	9,5	14,8	2400

*: 90 = East; 180 = South; 270 = West; 360 = North. **: wind direction recorded at 0600.

6.5.2 Migratory directions

Migratory direction on the morning of Sept. 4. was consistently SE for birds seen. Also for Barn Swallows, Meadow Pipits and White Wagtails, the direction of migration was between south to southeast. Compared to measured wind at Lista lighthouse (Tab. 6), the birds had a slight tailwind all morning, which wind direction ranged from 280 (morning – 06:00) to 250 (12:00 hours). Tail wind is a typical feature preferred weather conditions of migratory birds (Alerstam 1980, Newton 2010). The migration speed this morning was moderate, rated at between 35 and 45 km/h. This is a typical speed for low-altitude migrating passerine birds.

6.5.3 Migratory heights

Migratory height were estimated to the nearest 10 meter in relation to known heights of nearby tall buildings at the Lista airport. Overall, Barn Swallows migrated at a slightly higher altitude than wagtails and pipits (Tab. 7), median height 80 meters versus 40 meters for the pipits and wagtails. The difference between the species was obvious, overall results illustrate well that pipits and wagtails moved at low heights and mostly at the same elevation, and slightly more to the south, while the swallows clearly moved in a slightly higher air layer, somewhat faster, and consistently towards the southeast, also frequently seen chasing insects along the route.

Tab. 7. Migratory heights of flocks of pipits, wagtails and swallow at P1, Lista, September 4, 2018.

	Meadow Pipits	White Wagtails	Barn Swallows
Mean	41,7	43,3	83,1
SD	11,4	11,1	28,7
Median	40,0	40,0	60,0
CV (%)	27,2	25,7	34,5
N	79	15	19

6.5.4 Migratory corridors

For all three species of pipits, wagtails and swallows, migration was restricted to the west of the observation point P1 (Fig. 12), but the migration corridor extended also eastward throughout the test area and probably also with a somewhat greater width further to the northeast (see also observations from location P2). The number of birds recorded were therefore only a part of all migrants this morning. The movements was most intense between 08:00 and 09:00, but continued towards 11:00, but with a decreasing activity after 10:00 (recording was cancelled between 09:00 and 0950 - due to a project meeting regarding planning of test flights later in the week). The size distribution of bird flocks is shown in the next chapter.

6.5.5 Flock size and migratory dynamics

The Barn Swallows migrated in smaller flocks (Fig. 20), up to 30 individuals in one flock. Similar migratory behavior was observed for pipits and wagtails (Fig. 21 and Fig. 22), but with lower maximum flock size (17 and 15 individuals, respectively). For the swallows, the migratory intensity increased from the first to the second hour, but this was not observed for pipits and wagtails. Based on only a short observation period, and few species, was between-species variation in migratory behavior evident.

Fig. 20. Migration of Barn Swallows at P1 - Kitemill test area, September 4, 2018, shown as migratory flocks and individuals i a 2 hour period, 0700 til 0900. $N_{total} = 133$.

Fig. 21. Migration of Meadow Pipits at P1 - Kitemill test area, September 4, 2018, shown as migratory flocks and individuals i a 2 hour period $N_{total} = 132$.

Fig. 22. Migration of White Wagtails at P1 - Kitemill test area, September 4, 2018, shown as migratory flocks and individuals in a 2 hour period, 0700 til 0900. $N_{total} = 67$.

6.5.6 Other migratory species on September 4th.

A total of 23 species were observed during this observation period, distributed on 106 records and 565 individuals. The total number is not large compared to peak migration days on Lista, which can show thousands of birds during one days (Griffin et al. 1956). However, observations this morning illustrated well key issues regarding the type of data that should be logged over longer periods of time to document the use of local airspace at sites planned for AWES operation, i.e. migratory activity in relation to wind direction and wind speed, and not least at which heights the birds migrate (see further discussion under the risk assessments). In addition to the 3 species discussed above, 9 other passerine birds were observed, further 2 birds of prey (Sparrow Hawks and Kestrels; 2 and 4 individuals). Regarding goose migration, Greyleg Goose with recorded with 60 ind. (in 4 smaller flocks - all migrated east; one flock north of P1 and 3 flocks south of the airport). In addition, Barnacle Goose also migrated (25 ind.), but these geese migrated towards NV, south of the Lista airport. Of wader species, Common Snipes, Ruff, Golden Plover and Curlews were observed, some in smaller flocks. Golden Plovers was the most numerous with 69 ind. in 4 flocks, mainly seen in the airport's open fields, and with movements within the Lista airport area. A comprehensive overview of recorded species from location P1 is given in Appendix 2.

During the same morning, the overall bird migration diminished before noon, between 1100 -1200 (see also 3 passerien discussed in more details). Observations from the east of the test area (at location P2), showed still a few Barn Swallows and Chaffinches, while the the pipits had apparently stopped and initiated feeding in the farmland areas. Local flocks, with up to 30-40 birds, moved in several directions and mainly low above the ground, in search for better feeding places. At noon, several smaller flocks of Barn Swallows still migrated towards the SE, but with a clear decreasing intensity. Good numbers of Chaffinches, Siskins, Whinchats and Wheatears remained in the areas east of Lista airport, most birds in a feeding mode. In summary, September 4th showed up a fairly good migration day, with species typical of this time of the migratory season. The migration from the north and NW resulted in accumulated numbers of several species, with exceptions of swallows which did not show any signs of accumulation, but continued their migration towards SE. A clear relationship between wind conditions (tailwind) and migration activity came into place this day. Knowledge of migratory dynamics and the use of the airspace, including how birds migrate at different altitudes, is an important knowledge versus assessments of possible negative interaction with AWES systems. This day (September 4th), was later shown to be in contrast to the following days regarding migratory activity (see chapters below). Further, in the afternoon/evening,

monitoring of the test area was continued, without particularly large occurrences of birds being detected. Most important records were passing Cranes in the evening (5 ind.) - from SØ to NV (see the chapter discussing the local Cranes at Lista), as well as the presence of some Golden Plovers (42 ind.) and Northern Wheatear (10 - 15 ind.), all located at taxiways and in the nearby fields. Both species occurred in the test area over the next few days (see below). Regarding birds of prey, a Merlin was observed at P2 (east - see photo), as well as a Sparrow Hawk at P1 (to the west). Influx of many passerine birds during morning hours (see above), led to good hunting opportunities for birds of prey. Both raptors were observed hunting at low altitude (generally below 20 meters) in the fields and along forest edges.

6.5.7 Changes in weather conditions – and a near stop in migratory birds

Next morning, September 5, it was quiet, clear weather and with dewfall overnight. The wind direction during the morning (increased slightly) was more northerly (Tab. 6). Although it attracted some passerine birds this morning, there was significantly less bird recorded than the day before (see above). A few smaller flocks of Meadow Pipit, White wagtail, Barn Swallows, and Siskin, were observed from P1. Everyone was heading towards the SE, and at the same altitude as the day before (less than 50 meters altitude). At 08:00 hrs I concluded with low migration intensity. Of the few species seen, a Sparrow Hawk was recorded with successful hunting; a Meadow Pipit was taken only 40 meters from the observer (at P1). Later, another Sparrow Hawk was seen hunting at location P2. Otherwise, 2 cranes were observed from P1, towards the SE, at about 60 meters altitude (at 07:35).

From 0810 onwards, birds in the eastern part of the test area were focused. The result was many different passerines, and consistently with local movements in several directions, both resting and feeding birds such as Meadow Pipits, Yellow Wagtails, Robins, Whichats, Whitethroats, Chaffinches, Linnets, Siskins and Redpolls. The Curlew (2 ind.), was seen in the open fields by the local road in the east. This picture changed little over the morning, but the wind increased slightly, to about 3 - 4 m/s (see Tab. 6). Between 12:00 and 13:00, the occurrences of swallows moving toward the SE increased at varying altitudes; 2 flocks with a total of 83 ind. moved towards the SE, at the same time as they conducted insect hunting at about 100 meters altitude; a little later about 30 ind. - now at an altitude of between 150 and 200 meters; all north of P2 and the test area. A little later (at 12:40 pm), 2 smaller flocks (7 and 16 in.) moved towards SE at altitudes 50 to 80 meters. The Barn Swallows therefore showed somewhat variation in behavior on September 4 and 5, but all swallows moved towards the SE and mainly at a good heights. The detailed observations on these two September days are examples of the variation and dynamics that are typical of many bird species, related to prevailing weather conditions, time of day and phase of their migration.

Later during the day (Sept. 5th), weather conditions changed markedly as by 13:00, the temperature raised to above 20⁰ C, with cloudless weather and sun over most of the Lista, but otherwise with clouds in all directions. Many insects were noted active in the air, including the swarming of small beetles, i.e. good conditions for all insect eaters. Quiet, warm weather is also known as good conditions for migratory birds of prey. It was not long before the first birds of prey were observed moving to the east, first a Marsh Harrier, then 2 Buzzards, then 2 Sparrow Hawks, 2 Kestrels, a Goshawk and a Peregrine Falcon (the two later interacted at a height of 350 - 400 meters). All raptors were seen in thermal flights on upward warm air currents and all observed in the period between 13:00 to 16:00. For a bird of prey heading for Denmark, the conditions was certainly good. However, all were observed east of the test area (not central or west at Lista). In the same period, 3 flocks of Greyleg Goose migrated east, all in the zone between the main runway

and the North Hazel Road (totaling 106 individuals), i.e. they passed south of the Kitemill test area. They moved east at about 200 meters altitude. Even in the evening, some Greyls moved to the east (heard after dark). In total, the observations in and around the test area show a large variation regarding occurrence of species, in intensity of migration, different uses of altitude and also with the typical thermal flight of 5 different birds of prey. There were also differences in the use of different sections of the open farmland in and near the Kitemill test area.

6.5.8 Change in weather conditions – wind from the east, rain and test flights

The third day with fieldwork in September (6th) experienced a marked change in weather conditions, with wind from the east and rain (see Tab. 6). Monitoring and bird observations showed much of the same species as the days before, no migratory activity was observed. Under such weather conditions it is a common experience that migratory activity is suppressed, resulting in accumulation of birds in suitable staging areas (Alerstam 1980). Within the test Kitemill test site this was illustrated with good numbers of Wheatears on the taxways and nearby fields (Fig. 12). In addition, small flocks of Ringed Plover and Golden Plover were in the same areas. Most likely these waders had moved in during the night.

At noon the weather changed, with less rain and stronger winds, conditions suitable for Kitemill test flights. The kite turbine was made ready and test flights were performed through the day. The first flight occurred from 16.50 onwards. To assess effects and impacts on birds in the area, all birds were censused, zone-wise at and in the surroundings of the test area. Bird activities were then monitored as long as testing was in progress, i.e. both before, under and after the Kitemill test flights. Relative few bird species occurred in the test area and focus was set for how Golden Plover, Ringed Plover, Wheatears and Meadow Pipits respond to kite in the air (see Fig. 5). During the hours when the test kite was prepared, plovers moved much around in the local area and few plovers were left when the actual test flights were done. My observations/monitoring were done from a parked car during these testing sessions. In relation to moving cars, the plovers just moved short distances in nearby fields. That plovers left the area may have been a response to the general activity on ground, or they could be in the move. This left me in a situation where only Wheatears (Fig. 25) remained for studies of possible impacts of the Kitemill test flights. During the next hour when the kite was in the air, there was nearly a constant number of birds at the taxways (around 15 birds), both before, under and after the test flights (see also below).

Regarding other birds observed this afternoon, small flocks of Greylag Goose moved towards east, but all south of the test area (where they also used to migrate the days before). In total 113 geese were seen, from 7 smaller flocks. Regarding birds of prey, a Merlin hunted low in the area, in fact right through the test area, without any sign of response to the testing activity. Further, a Peregrine falcon sat on the runway south of the test site (P1), without any sign of response to the flying kite. At ground distance: about 200 meter. Other species were few as several Skylarks, White Wagtails and Siskin were recorded passing by. Wagtails passed with two occasions under the flying kite, without showing any response. One shorebird, Wood sandpiper *Tringa glareola*, flew into the test area from the north. Direction was just towards the line under the kite. The sandpiper response was to turn around, retracting north again where it landed in the field about 100 meter away. This incident was recorded as a clear case of avoidance (at time 17.20), the only recorded during the monitoring sessions. The disappearance of plover before the kite was in the air, may just be a response to the general human activity on the ground (4 persons from the Kitemill team was in action). Such response to human activity, through disturbance, is a common seen effect, well documented in numerous studies regarding human outdoors activities (Smit & Visser 1993, Gill et

al. 1996). Conclusions based on these monitoring and test sessions, based on recording birds occurrence and behaviour both before, under and after the test flights, is the relatively few birds was in the area, including few bird species (mainly Wheatears), and there was no change in number throughout the test period. Wheatears were mostly engaged in searching for food at or near the taxeways (see Fig. 25). No collisions were recorded, but interesting one shorebird (the Wood Sandpiper) responded with an avoidance response to the kite/line or both. Behaviour like this is maybe difficult to quantify, but certainly more fieldwork is needed before proper impact assessment could be done. Protocols should also include control areas, i.e. using a BACI-strategy (cf. Underwood 1994).

Fig. 23. Bad weather with unfavorable wind, rain and poor visibility can cause many migratory birds to stop for breaks and food searches. Here a Ringed Plover (young bird) on the taxway in the Kitemill test area. September 6, 2018. Photo: A. Håland

Fig. 24. Along with the Ringed Plover and Wheatears, some Golden Plovers were initially in the test area for a rest. Golden Plovers has been detected frequently and in gatherings of over 500 individuals at the Lista Airport, i.e. the Golden Plover is a characteristic species during the autumn migration at Lista. September 6, 2018. Photo: A. Håland.

Fig. 25. Several 10s of Wheatears used the taxiway in the Kitemill test area, but they did not show any visible response to the test flights conducted close to the birds, neither did their number in the area drop during the test flights. September 6th. 2018. Photo: A. Håland.

7 IMPACT FACTORS AND RISK ASSESSMENTS

All new human interventions and/or activities have a built-in potential for undesirable and adverse effects on nature, plants and animals. Energy production in many forms is one sector, where hydropower in particular is a mainstay in Norway, in terms of electricity production. The influence on biodiversity may be great, as is the knowledge with research over many decades (Faugli et al. (1994), Håland & Faugli (1994), Eie (2006)). Relatively new, at least on a large scale, is the utilization of wind as an energy carrier. In Norway, and in the world, many wind turbines have been built, and many plants are being planned, including in Norway. The impacts on nature may be severe, but central to the question is how wind turbines, individually and collectively, affect birds (and partly bats), populations (cf. Rydell et al. 2017). In the main focus of such conflict themes, the issue is how of building and operating wind turbines leads to increased mortality of birds, a result of collisions with wind turbines (including rotor blades and the tower itself). Research so far have been inconsistent regarding levels of mortality, but many studies have shown that the image is fairly clear: mortality is limited (as measured by total number of killed per turbine per year), but in some cases mortality may be high. The overall negative impact can also be great, especially for migratory species that are exposed to many wind power plants, both in staging areas, along the migratory paths and in the winter quarters, in addition to impacts in their breeding areas. When it comes to local power plants, the conclusion is that by placing a wind power plant in the wrong place, the damage can be so great that it cannot be accepted. Another conclusion is that all localities are unique in terms of occurrence of birds and how birds use the airspace locally. The conclusions give from reviews of research, is that all relevant locations for new plants are undergoing thorough mapping and investigation to determine the potential for damage.

The question focused in this project is then how a new technology, high-altitude wind energy systems (AWES), falls into this spectrum of technologies that will carry the production of renewable energy in the future (solar, wind, water, geothermal, tidal, etc.). Kitemill's concept, where testing and innovation is in process, is one of several types of AWES currently under development, but in relation to how realization and utilization in larger production areas can affect nature and biodiversity in general, and birds and bird fauna in particular, there is no research and knowledge to find. There is currently no specific research available regarding the impact on birds, cf. European Commission (2016) report focusing on knowledge gaps in this field. The Lista project in 2018, linked to Kitemill's ongoing testing activity with various kite turbines, is therefore a first step towards more insight into whether and how AWES plants have a negative impact on birds (and other parts of biodiversity). In assessing what the 2018 results in the Lista project can say about the risk of negative impact and possible mortality on birds, there are many different factors that need to be focused and it is important in a research start-up phase to have a broad approach to the problem. The present study is not an formal impact assessment, but it may initially be useful to have a slightly wider perspective of how Kitemill's testing activities may have affected the natural environment at Lista Airport in general and birds in particular. In the following chapters, therefore, the main influencing factors related to new energy plants are briefly discussed.

7.1 Physical impacts

The layout of the Kitemill plant and principles regarding energy production are shown in Chapter 2. An overview of the test areas with several use zones (related to different wind conditions) is shown in Fig. 9. The plant is mounted on one of the existing taxways and has not resulted in any new

physical impact on local ecosystems. When using the smaller, mobile unit, the runway/taxway and adjoining pitch areas are used. Conclusion: no physical impacts have been made in the natural environment in connection with the completed test program so far (an overview given in chapter 3), or no negative consequence regarding physical impacts in nature.

7.2 Disturbances

Conducting test flights in a restricted area necessarily involves some human activities; installation of the facility, preparation of test flights and implementation of test flights. Activities are transport (with cars) and traffic related to test activities. We find this type of disturbance in all human outdoor activities, sometimes with negative effects on nature and birds (cf. Gill et al. 1996, Smit & Visser (1993). Relatively much research exists on how our outdoor activities impact birds (and other organisms). Thus, this issue is not elaborated on here, but direct human-related disruptions related to test run of the Kitemill plant have been the focus of the field work in 2018, in parallel with the focus on testing the kite turbine itself. Potential impacts have therefore been discussed in other chapters in the report.

7.3 Noise

Noise is an independent influencing factor, among other things, noise is part of the concept of pollution in national legislation (Pollution Control Act). Noise can be measured, from barely audible to loud and directly harmful noise levels. Noise is also part of the previous focal point, interference, ie it may be noise that is the direct mechanism of action in triggering disturbances on nature and here - birds, both alone and in combination with visual stimuli. Kitemill's concept consists of flight of a kite attached to a line, that there is no engine involved (except when using larger kites where small rotors (as a drone) lifts the kite to the desired height). Test flights with the smaller, mobile kite, has been the focus of this project in the period June to September 2018. It flies in part as a low-noise sail plane, but when running the kite in loops (see review of the Kitemill concept), some sound is produced, both from the line and also from the kite itself. For the human ear, the sounds are perceived as weak, but loud enough that it can have an effect on birds which in turn can avoid that test area, or when flying close to the kite and line in operation. It may be difficult at times to distinguish effects from the sound or whether it is the visual impression of the kite in the air that the birds are responding to (see also below).

7.4 Collisions

When it comes to the construction and operation of traditional wind turbines, the above-mentioned factors of influence are also important in assessing whether birds are negatively affected or not. Many studies have shown that birds often avoid single turbines, or entire wind power plants, by flying between the turbines, or outside or above the wind turbines, or at large turbines, such as offshore wind turbines, flying low and below the turbine rotors (Lukas et al. (2007)), Everaert (2014), Brabrant et al. (2015), Rydell et al. (2017). But the most important factor is whether wind turbines act as a collision object, i.e. whether birds fly into the physical structures and are injured or die (usually the last). The same issues are relevant regarding AWES installations, although they are conceptual and physically different from traditional wind turbines with an a) a line between ground turbine and kite and b) a kite flying at high speed (or another design; many different designs/structures are currently undergoing testing globally - see European Commission (2016)).

The following discuss potential negative impacts from a AWES plants, and/or impacts from each of the main components in a high-wind energy system (such as the Kitemill concept).

The line, which is pulled out from a drum on the ground, is thin and at some distance with a limited visibility (for the human eye). The length of the line during a test flight is related to the flying height of the kite, which may be a few hundred meters or theoretically several thousand meters (Fig. 26). The line is at rest while the kite is kept at a stable peak, but moves quickly when the kite is in a loop (Fig. 26). The used impacted airspace then goes from a 2-dimensional to a 3-dimensional space, where the velocity of the line is greatest near the kite, and the least near the ground. Impacted air space is largest near the kite, and smallest near the ground. Regarding flying birds, both the line and the kite may be a risk factor, in the same way as the rotor blades at conventional wind turbines, especially when the kite moves in great speed during the loops (Fig. 26).

Fig. 26. Flying with the Kitemill kite (and similar designs) establishes a physical element in the airspace that birds can collide with (or avoid - see text). How large the affected airspace is depends primarily on how large the kite system is, ie how large the circle is when the kite is flown, as well as how high in the air the kite is flown. The latter determines how much airspace is affected. Source: Kitemill AS

7.5 Theoretical and observed responses to test flights

Birds in flight within the test area at Lista can respond to test flights in different ways, discussed below both with a logical starting point, i.e. theoretical behavioural responses that may generate several impact hypotheses. Further, on the basis of fieldwork during breeding period (in June 2018) and during the migration period (early September 2018), empirical results are discussed.

7.5.1 Responses during the breeding period – Skylark and Meadow Pipit

During the breeding season, bird censuses and monitoring were made during two 3-days sessions in June. It was quickly clarified that there were a limited number of species established as breeding species in and near the Kitemill test area, and therefore few species at risk regarding contact/conflict with Kitemill's test flight activities. Test flights have been, and are being conducted, in

defined sectors at the Lista airport, varied in relation to wind conditions (wind direction primarily). With performing test flights with larger kites, a larger airspace is affected, even over forested areas. In this project, only the small kite system were used in the test flights (see Fig. 9 for affected areas).

The open farmland had two breeding species which occurred frequently, the Skylark and the Meadow Pipit. Both species appeared fairly common in the test area and nearest surroundings, reflected in the point census. Both species were active during all 6 days in June, and in particular, Skylarks was a characteristic breeding species within a wider area of the Lista airport. This species is currently nationally red-listed (VU - cf. Henriksen & Hilmo 2015), i.e. the local breeding population certainly have an interest at the national level. From each section of the test area, from P1 in the west to P2 in the east, it was typical to hear 2 and 3 singing Skylarks, and sometimes up to 5 singing males, from the same observation point. The local population in the test area is therefore most probably larger than 15 pairs, i.e. a good local population.

The Kitemill test activities during spring 2018 (and earlier - see overview in the report), does not seem to have affected the local breeding population of Skylarks, although smaller changes in the local population cannot be detected without detailed ecological studies before, during and after test activities, and then also with field data from at least one control area (BACI methodology, cf. Underwood 1994). The Skylark is characteristic species because of the male's territorial song in the open air space, the usual altitude of song flights is 40 to 100 meters. Duration of the songsflights is also exceptional, with each song session lasting up to 15-20 minutes. Here, the Skylarks are different from the Meadow Pipits, which have a much shorter song flights, normally with a duration of 10 to 15 seconds, and with less height in the flights, usually up to 30 - 40 meters. This different use of the airspace, in principle, leads Skylarks into a higher risk class versus the use of a AWES operations and especially interaction with the line connected to the kite. With regard to occurrences of birds in the test area (and the surrounding area) versus testing activities, birds were mapped with zone monitoring both west and east in the test area, the mapping was done from 04:00 to 11:30 on June 25th. Later, the test flight was carried out from noon (11.30) onwards throughout the day until 21:00 in the evening. All 5 test flights that days were monitored continuously. It was not observed that any birds collided with line or kite (all species observed) during the trails. Also, no avoidance actions was observed (avoidance is when the bird change course to avoid contact or collisions with the line or kite). Avoidance behaviour at several levels is also a relevant aspect regarding traditional wind turbines (see Evereart 2014). For the established breeding species (Skylarks and Meadow Pipits), such avoidance behaviour was not observed, but it is possible that some individuals moved slightly away from the ground area under the kite while testing was in progress, unnoticed for the human eye. However, the Skylarks in the area maintained a frequent singing activity close to the test flight area itself, including one male with song flights less than 100 meters from the kite flight area. The same also applies with Meadow Pipits, frequently observed singing (with song flights) during the Kitemill testing. At 16:26 and later, several observations were made with pipit song flights in the immediate area (down to 50 meters from a vertical line from the flying kite). As stated, no direct interactions (collisions/close contacts) with line or kite were observed for these 2 species during this testing day.

7.5.2 Respons during the breeding period – Swift and Barn Swallow

Surveying and monitoring over 4 days before the test flights showed that the Swift and Barn Swallow both hunted their aerial insects in and near the test area, as well as the surrounding landscape on Lista (see discussion and details otherwise in the report). With a specialized

adaptation to insect hunting in open the air, sometimes up to relatively high altitudes, both species can, as a rule, be classified as risk species with regard to high wind energy systems. Observations during the test flights in June, however, shown otherwise; no Swift were observed during the entire test flights, and only limited of Barn Swallows. Recorded Barn Swallows, both before and after the test flights, all flew very low during their insect hunt, consistently less than 1 meter above the ground. This low-flying is typical of barn swallowers when there is some wind. Then the insects stay low above the ground, or even down in the grass, consequently the swallows have to hunt where the prey is. At a mean wind force (this test day had fresh wind from west), the swallows generally hunt low, and often close to deciduous forests nearby the test area. In cooler weather, or during rainfall, swallows also hunt much over water, low and often close to the water surface, or even picking insects from the water surface itself. Conclusion: when there is enough wind for test flying (as on June 25, 2018), the Barn Swallows fly low and are at little risk in the higher air strata where the Kitemill kite flew. Otherwise, the local swallows did not seem to care about the test flights; at several occations (at 16:15 and 16:48), two Barn Swallows passed under the kite when the test was in progress, and they showed no sign of negative response as they hunted close by. While the Barn Swallows changed hunting behavior, and especially with low hunting flights, Swifts, during windy conditions other usuitable weather conditions, may find themselves in completely different hunting areas, geographically speaking. Swifts are reasonably extreme as they can fly several thousand km in search for their insect food, sometimes around large pressure systems (cf. Alerstam 1982). They can also do this with chicks in their nest. Swifts may therefore frequently disappear locally, before they reappear. Avaiability of insect prey is the key factor. The fact that Swifts were not seen in the test area during the testing day is therefore not an unexpected result, compared to the increasing high wind on Lista that day. One detail may be that Swifts were observed at P1 in the morning hours (between 06:30 and 08:00; 3 times and all at relatively low altitude (15 m, 20 m and low over forests)). After that no observations were made throughout this day. On other days, in warm, quiet weather, the Swifts showed a great activity locally, often flying at several hundred meters altitude (see the species report in the report).

7.5.3 Respons during the breeding period – Lesser Black-backed Gull

Lesser Black-backed Gulls, which breed in large colonies on islands off the Lista (e.g. on Rauna in particular - cf. Fylkesmannen 2015), used the open farmland on Lista to a large extent, both fields within the airport and the test area and outside, but only temporarily. During the first field sessions in June, gulls occurred in large numbers during a period when farmers mowed and fertilized the fields. This is well documented, see details earlier in the report. On the day of test flying (June 25th), there were many seagulls to watch in the morning hours, including flocks with up to 300 individuals, bothin fields at P1 and a little to the west. A few Herring Gulls were also seen in the flocks. The seagulls were feeding and moved around a lot. After 7 am there were fewer/few seagulls in and around the test area, but from about 1 pm the number increased slightly as single seagulls came in from the south; in flight altitudes around 20-30 meters. At the start of the Kitemill test flights (12:30), there were several smaller flocks in the surrounding area, including 7 adults about 100 meters north of the test area at P1. Later, the flock increased to 12 adults, all coming in from the SE or south, all flying low over the fields in the westerly wind. On 5 occasions they flew to the grazing area in the north, and than directly under the kite looping in the air, apparently without caring for either the line or the kite (4, 5, 1, 2 and 1 adult birds were observed on these occations, respectively). The last gull came in from the SE, at a height of 25 meters, with a falling kite over it, but no response was observed. The gulls on the ground in the north, where the flock had increased

to over 20 adults, had meanwhile moved closer to the actual test area (with both people and activity on the ground and kite in the air), all eagerly feeding and with no signs of response or avoiding the test area. Throughout the day, the gulls seem to neglect completely the test flights, both flying to and from the test area. An exception was observed at 13:11 when an adult seagull came in from the SE, in about 30 meters altitude, flying almost on the kite line during a test flight. This gull changed its course abruptly, flew further, but now low, and returned to the southern fields. This incident shows an active avoidance or "micro-avoidance" (cf. Everaert (2014), i.e. an abrupt avoidance close to a certain physical element (here the kite line). This shows that the line can be a risk factor for flying gulls, even though the majority of the gulls did not show a negative response to the test activity and flights itself. The limited visibility of the line is here a factor that may affect the distance the bird could detect the line. At the current flight altitude of the seagulls, the line moved relatively little horizontally, but the movement could nevertheless be why the gull discovered the line and departed/changed course in time. Similar behavior/response is relatively common with seagulls towards conventional wind turbines (Everaert 2014), i.e. a response close to the turbine's rotorblade. The behavior of gulls at Lista, showing mostly no or little response to the test activity and test flights, can be an example of habituation. The gulls on Lista (and elsewhere on the coast) are in the breeding colonies from the beginning of April (normal arrival time), and they experienced the Kitemill test activity during both April and May 2018. Gulls, when they are first grown to adult age, can live quite a long time, which imply that the gulls in the test area during the test flights, may have been here all the years before (see overview of Kitemill test flight early years – Tab. 1), and experienced the Kitemill test activities. In general, gull also adapt well to live close to humans, including exploitation of human resources (food).

A related aspect, described in the report, is the gulls' use of the airspace up to several hundred meters in height (and thus in altitudes actual for looping kites). Such behavior, however, happens mainly on hot days and with little wind, with thermal flights similar to birds of prey. But under such weather conditions it is not relevant to fly neither testflights nor production flights with AWES, i.e. the potential for conflict with seagulls on such days is very low.

7.5.4 Rare species during the breeding period – Marsh Harrier and Crane

On the basis of my own mapping and observations during 6 days in June and 3 days in September, (and other available data - cf. Artskart), I have focused two species of conservation interest which breed at Lista, but some distance away from the Kitemill test site, the Marsh harrier and the Crane. The former has a few breeding species in Norway, with Lista as the classic area, and with the lake Slevdalsvannet as the central area of activity for the species. The species is currently national red list (in cat. VU). The Crane is on the rise in Norway, but still few on Lista (although very many observations are available - see analysis of their occurrence earlier in the report). Birds of prey are generally considered a risk group with respect to collisions with wind turbines, while cranes belong to a group that occasionally uses soaring-gliding techniques, i.e. a flight behavior that results in poorer maneuverability than many other species.

Cranes was heard from P1 in the test area in June, but not observed (but seen in September). Sivhauk was seen regularly, but not in the test area itself. On the day of test flying with Kitemill, none of these 2 species were seen in the area, despite almost continuous observing activity from 04:00 to 21:00 (interrupted only by a few short breaks). Therefore, these two species with a potential for conflict with Kitemill's AWES in operation, nothing happened that could provide further knowledge about their vulnerability versus operation of a high-wind energy system. However, with few individuals in the local populations (both species), the likelihood of crossing the area with the

kite in the air is low. There is also a possibility that, when observing the kite itself in flight (at medium altitudes as in test flights until 2018), they may respond by avoiding the test area (type response: macro-avoidance). Only a more comprehensive monitoring/observation activity, and at sites with more birds, can determine how such species responds to operational kites in the air.

7.5.5 Risks assessed in relation to flight type, behaviour and flying heights

The field work on Lista in June documented well which bird species are found in and near the test area. Relatively few species nest in the open countryside, but there are many more species associated with edge zones, forests and also in the more developed areas (for example in The business park at Lista Airport). An overview of relevant bird species has been reported and discussed earlier in the report, using both point censuses, zone mapping and monitoring birds behaviour and area use at Lista. Some bird species are common, many are scarce and some even rare and with few breeding pairs. Regarding risk assessments, an overview of species and their occurrence/numbers is the first factor in a risk model. In addition comes knowledge about species ecology and habitat use (some species prefer habitat types within the test area, other species are associated with other habitat types in the surrounding landscape). Knowledge of their habitat preference is enough to exclude many species as potential risk species for conflict with an AWES in operation, cf. my focus on the species that used the test area during breeding season in June 2018 (see above). Furthermore, variation and dynamics with regard to flight behavior and altitude come in as important parameters, as illustrated by discussion of the behavior of both seagulls, swallows, pipits, Skylarks, Swifts, birds of prey, etc. Finally, the same species may have different connection to a given area/site, here Kitemill's test area, through the different phases of the year. Further, there may be differences between how a given species behave in the breeding season versus the migratory season (see also the discussion of birds migratory behavior). Occurrence itself, as it may appear in observational databases (such as Artskart), is by far not enough to clarify the level of risks and conflicts for a given species. It specific knowledge about their specific habitat use, their flight behavior and use of the airspace through various phases of nesting and annual cycles, that are controlling factors and which details must be clarified for each species, and at each test site/operational area. At Lista, between 200 and 250 bird species are observed annually, a high number that can be linked to high activity of local birdwatchers, but also to the operation of the Lista bird station. Among the large range of species observed annually on Lista, only parts of the spectrum of bird species will actually be exposed to risk from a AWES such as that of which Kitemill is currently testing. This project, completed in 2018 (this report), has clarified some important issues, with a significantly lower level of conflict than could theoretically be assumed on matters based on Lista's reputation as an nationally important bird area.

The inverse relationship between test activity (which requires a good deal of wind - preferably over 6-8 m/s at ground level) and birds' use of airspace under different weather conditions, including their use of higher air strata at low winds, is central to a risk model and the risk assessment process. The relationship between wind strength, test flight and birds' flight activity and, not least, bird's flight altitudes, is very important, both during the breeding season (see above) and during migration seasons (see later in the report). By and large, most birds migrate at night (Griffin et al. 1956, Alerstam 1982, Karlsson et al. 2011, Kemp et al. 2012, La Sorte et al. 2015a, b, Nilsson 2015, van Doren et al. 2017, Carbrera -Cruz et al. 2017), and preferably with clear skies and low winds. Migration during the day are also typical of some species, or many species that mainly migrate at night can extend the migration into the light hours of the morning (this report).

Research on bird traits, migratory dynamics and migratory behavior shows marked differences between different study areas and at different phases of the annual cycle, and the clear recommendations have been given that each area of action must be studied individually to clarify the many questions and the wide variety of birds that migrate between nesting areas and winter quarters (or even between areas in connection with their moult/the moult migration (Salomonsen 1968) or during feeding trips throughout the year). Existing ecological and applied knowledge may be transferable versus risk assessments in relation to new technological solutions (such as Kitemill), but always with limitations driven by a wide range of impacting environmental factors and differences between bird species found in geographically different areas.

Fig. 27. Testing a AWES, such as Kitemill, need sufficient wind, but with increasing wind force many birds change their habitat use and flight behavior, consequently there is often a lower risk for negative interactions with the AWES in operation. Both wind direction and wind force are important factors regarding both test flying with Kitemill and the birds use of the open air. 6. sept. 2018. Foto: A. Håland.

7.6 Risk assessment in relation 2018 test flights

The previous chapters have discuss if operation of Kitemill's kite turbine have risks and unwanted, negative impacts on birds at Lista, during the breeding time and during the migration periods. The Kitemill small plant has not resulted in any physical impacts on the local environment. The test activities is fairly low on an annual basis (about 20 test days a year), i.e. local disturbances are considered moderate to low. Testing of the AWES produces little noise, i.e. an impact factor that normally is associated with other human activities are present to a small extent. In relation to the core problems associated with AWES and birds 'risk of collision with line/kite, injury and death, there is a wide range of aspects in birds' dynamic use of areas and airspace/altitude, which may attenuate risks and conflict levels. All test activity by Kitemill has so has been carried out during the day, and most of the time between 11 am and 7 pm, i.e. for a period of the day when the activity on birds is fairly low/lower than in the morning hours and at night. Through this fact, the level of conflict with birds during the test periods has been substantially reduced, intentionally or not. If we look at the bird's migration time, during spring and autumn, the large number of birds migrate at night (see references), and without test activities during the night, the level of conflict is also significantly reduced during the birds' migration periods. However, despite this, a significant number of birds do migrate during the day (this report, see also references). On the basis that birds migrate over long periods of time in the annual cycle, most during March to May in the spring; and from late July to early November during the fall season, and with different bird species at different times (early or late in the migratory periods), this 2018 pilot study at Lista has only studied a short period (and thus a limited number of migratory species). Therefore, there is a

need for a similar observation program at other times during the birds migration, both during spring and autumn. This is to clarify the risk and conflict potential for Lista specific, cf. international research experience on the great variation between different geographical areas with regards to interactions between wind power plants and birds. Some of the knowledge is probably transferable, not least how the different bird species relate to local weather conditions in terms of flight activity, flight behavior and altitudes and use of airspace (Stebbins 1906, Alerstam 1982, Lechti & Schaller 1999, Lechti et al. 2000, Shamoun -Baranes & van Gastern 2011, Kalhert et al. 2012, Doctor et al. 2013, La Sorte et al. 2015, Bäckman et al. 2017, Senner et al. 2018), or examples from the 2018 migration on Lista (this report).

8 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

8.1 Background

Since 2008, Kitemill AS has been working on the development of a new concept of harvesting wind resources at higher altitudes than standard wind turbines, using what is called Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWES). Kitemill has been working on testing / testing its concept for several years, an overview test flight is provided in the report. In connection with applications for permits for a continued test program on Lista, a decision by the local planning authority, Farsund Municipality, in the spring of 2018, set requirements for the preparation of a monitoring plan related to continued testing of Kitemill's high-wind facilities. At the heart of the decision was the desire for knowledge related to the question of whether the testing activities can have negative effects on birds and bird populations. NNI prepared a proposal for a plan and plan (Håland 2018), a plan that was approved a little later. The academic approach in the program has been two-fold: 1) establishing knowledge about species using the test area at Lista Airport and 2) monitoring the implementation of test flights with the high-wind facility. The first factor in a risk model is which species are present and in what quantities, the second is in what risk level the individual bird species is versus kites in the air. Based on an approved plan, field work at Lista Airport was carried out in June and September 2018, ie during the breeding season of the birds and for a period during the autumn migration.

8.2 Fieldwork and results from the breeding period

The first field session was conducted in mid-June, with the main focus on mapping breeding birds in the Kitemill test area, in the near-influence area as well as in the surrounding area on Lista, which could probably recruit birds into the test area. The second field session was carried out a little later in June, with a focus on Kitemill tests, including mapping and monitoring of birds in the area before, during and after the test flights. A total of 6 field days were completed in June where the focus was on birds during the breeding season and the evaluation of possible negative impacts on birds.

8.3 Fieldwork and results from the migration period

The third, and last, field session was carried out at the beginning of September, i.e. in an important phase during the autumn migration. Included in the work in September was also monitoring of Kitemill test flights. One goal was to gain knowledge of bird movement and migratory behaviour in the test area, as well as how the test area was located in relation to the relevant migration corridors. Another important issue is the birds' migratory behavior and the use of different altitude levels in the airspace. Much research exists on such topics (cf. some referenced studies), but the transfer value in terms of knowledge is variable. One conclusion that can be drawn is that the bird's many facets vary widely from place to place, ie knowledge of behavioral conditions with regard to the dynamics of the migration, i.e. the migration's variation in time and space, is area-specific and consequently, in relation to interaction with AWES birds must be studied locally in all cases.

Monitoring of the migration in the test area and the surrounding area in September illustrated well a distinctive feature of bird migration; the birds migrate a lot on some days and little on others. The migration intensity of most bird species is largely controlled by the weather conditions, and in

particular wind conditions and wind direction. Most species migrate at night, although many species also migrate during the day and some species do both. This is well documented in many studies on bird migration (cf. Alerstam 1980, Newton 2010). On one day on Lista, a regular migration was made through Kitemill's test area, mostly passerine bird species, but also migration in a number of species in other species groups. In terms of elevation, the visible migration in the morning, until noon, was relatively low, most of them flew below 200 meters. Migratory movements, direction and height, were logged for all species during this field session (see results). Later days the migration was greatly reduced or almost absent. On a hot September day (above 20°C), the birds behaved differently, including thermal flights/soaring flights in several birds of prey. Species strongly associated with the airspace throughout their life, i.e. on Lista typical the Swifts and Barn Swallows, use higher air strata when air is warm, but in wind (and in rain) their behavior and habitat use change to low flying, often close to meadows, forests and wetland/water habitats. These birds provide a good example regarding the variation in flight behavior and thereby variation in the risk of unwanted contact with the Kitemill AWES in operation. In the case of Kitemill test activities, they were done only at wind speeds above 6 m/s, i.e. there is an inverse relationship between several bird species using a slightly higher air layer and test flights; during low wind there is no test flight and many bird species may use higher air layers without risks. With sufficient winds, test can be performed, but then many of the bird species fly low and near ground, trees and water/wetland.

Visual monitoring of bird migration in the test area at the beginning of September 2018 was naturally enough done in the bright part of the day, from sunrise to sunset. It is well documented that the vast majority of bird migration occurs at night, and preferably under favorable weather conditions. This relationship is well documented in the research literature (see references). In a risk assessment perspective versus Kitemill test flights, all tests have taken place during the day, and then significantly during the times between 11:00 to 19:00 (Tab. 1), i.e. in the previous and 2018 test activities, there has been little overlap between the bird's most important periods of migratory activity (night and morning) and the test flights, and thus also a low risk of negative interaction between Kitemill's plants and birds. Together with test flying on days with good winds/high winds, this means that overall the test activity has so far been most likely have performed with low risk for birds in the Lista area.

8.4 Overall assessment of risk and negative impacts

Direct monitoring of tests in June and September showed that 1) test activities were generally restricted to birds in the test area itself, and 2) there was a low frequency regarding birds' interaction with line and kite. No collisions were recorded, and only 2 cases of line avoidance (micro-avoidance) were seen (one for Lesser Black-backed gull in June and 1 for Wood Sandpiper (a wader) in September). Otherwise, the birds in the area showed a relatively high tolerance for ongoing test activities, both for breeding birds in the test area (Skylarks and Meadow Pipits), and also for the species that were present during the migratory period in September. When it comes to birds that are long-lived, such as seagulls, and who can use a given area year after year, one cannot ignore that habituation to the test activity and test flying take place, although it is more likely that the gull general tolerance to human activities is at work at Lista also. Gulls are also familiar with agricultural activities related to fertilization and mowing of the fields in the airport area (and otherwise on Lista). Species associated with the test area during the breeding season in June generally continued their normal activities (feeding and search of prey, singing activity or

resting), with no direct negative response detected. Specific avoidance of the test area ("disturbance effect") is difficult to detect without more detailed studies, but for species that breed in the area, such as the red-listed Skylark, such avoidance was not apparent or working at a very moderate level. As the testing activity has mostly been of short duration/short test sessions, this means that local birds can quickly return to exploited habitat and food resources they may have been disturbed from temporarily. An issue that is briefly discussed in the report is that the test activity during the birds' most important establishment period in the spring, such as nesting, egg laying and hatching, may have led some pair, such as Skylarks and Meadow Pipits, to have given up nesting and moved away from the most disturbed parts of the Kitemill test area. Such questions can only be answered by detailed examination during this part of the breeding period, in the test area and also in a control area. That said, the extent of the affected area is not very large, seen from the perspective of the entire Lista airport area (and the larger farmland area at Lista). Such disturbance is also limited in relation to the effects of intensive farming operations on farmland birds (which may affect breeding birds - with the loss of both nests and young). But, from a birds perspective, it's a matter of cumulative effects, in relation to successful breeding or not.

In summary, it can be concluded that the Kitemill operations of test flights mainly during the daytime hours, and mainly on days with moderate to high winds, comes little in direct conflict with nesting and migratory birds on Lista. The level of disturbance/negative impact in the breeding period is also low, and with a low risk of direct interaction with local birds (collisions and injury/death). This assessment and conclusion is linked to the test activities carried out under direct monitoring in June 2018, but also to the fact that test flights were conducted over time at limited times (daytime/afternoon) and in weather conditions (medium to high winds) where birds use slightly higher air layers very where the kite flies. Total risk versus unwanted impacts to birds is low, due to the fact that most of the bird migration occurs in the night (the night migration often starts right after sunset and ends in the morning twilight). In the test area, day-migrating birds (which can often be an extension of the night migration into the morning hours on good migration days), were recorded using the lower air strata, for several species below 50 meters in height, and for most species lower than 200 meters in height. For some species of particular conservation interest, such as Marsh Harrier and Cranes, the total number of birds in the Lista area is low (both species), and in 2018 with the use of the landscape and habitats that are only slightly overlapping with the test area (Marsh Harrier), or with very few observations in and at the test area (Cranes). The monitoring in 2018 is carried out during summer time - in June (late in bird's nesting season) and during early autumn, and with overall weather conditions that have been special this year. Low rainfall in the summer of 2018 resulted in dry fields, which may have affected some bird species' use of the airport area, and thus the local movement patterns. This contrasts with the more rainy years/periods which can quickly affect birds' land use in the open and flat landscape of Lista. A warm and dry summer is one of the great variety that belongs to the world of birds when it comes to temporal and numerical behavior, flight behavior and use of the airspace. Therefore, a comprehensive approach should be used in overall risk assessments, which in turn requires the building up of solid knowledge of each area where AWES installations and operations are actual. For mitigated measures that can counteract undesirable effects, such knowledge is of the utmost importance.

The project's activities at Lista in 2018 have been limited in scope, but have provided valuable insights and knowledge about local birds regarding their behavior and habitat use, and not least insights into the birds' response to flight with Kitemill's high wind energy system.

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10 APPENDIX 1 SPECIES LIST

Species list based on fieldwork during June and September 2018. All: records A. Håland, NNN.

Lista 2018 Species	June			September		
	Test area	Influence area	Outer landscape	Test area	Influence area	Outer landscape
Mute Swan			x			
Canada Goose		x				
Barnacle Goose		x				x
Bar-headed Goose			x			
Greyleg Goose	x	x	x	x	x	x
Shelduck			x			
Mallard		x	x			x
Eurasian Teal						x
Tufted Duck			x			
Red-breasted Merganser			x			x
Velvet Scoter			x			x
Common Eider						x
Long-tailed Duck						x
Crested Grebe			x			
Cormorant	x	x	x			x
Marsh Herrier		x	x	x	x	x
Common Buzzard						x
Sparrow Hawk				x	x	x
Goshawk						x
Kestrel				x	x	x
Hobby				x	x	
Perergrine Falcon	x			x	x	
Merlin				x	x	
Crane		x	x	x	x	
Oystercatcher			x			
Common Snipe				x	x	
Golden Plover				x	x	x
Ringed Plover	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ruff				x	x	
Redshank		x	x			
Greenshank					x	
Wood Sandpiper				x		
Dunlin					x	x
Turnstone						x
Bar-tailed Godwit						x
Whimbrel		x				x
Curlew		x	x	x		x
Common Gull		x	x			x
Lesser Black-backed Gull	x	x	x			x
Herring Gull	x	x	x			x
Great Black-backed Gull			x			x
Collared Dove		x	x			x
Wood Pigeon	x	x	x	x		
Great Spotted Woodpecker					x	
Swift	x	x	x			
Barn Swallow	x	x	x	x	x	x

Appendix 1 Species list

Sand Martin		x				
Tree Pipit	x	x		x		
Meadow Pipit	x	x	x	x	x	x
Skylark	x	x	x	x	x	
White Wagtail	x	x	x	x	x	x
Yellow Wagtail					x	
Starling	x	x	x			
Blackcap		x	x			
Garden Warbler	x	x	x			
Whitethroat	x	x	x	x	x	
Chiffchaff		x	x			
Willow Warbler	x	x	x			
Sedge Warbler		x	x			
Pied Flycatcher			x			
Robin	x	x	x	x	x	
Wheatear	x	x	x	x	x	x
Whinchat	x	x	x	x	x	
Song Trush		x				
Blackbird	x	x	x			x
Fieldfare	x	x	x			
Blue Tit		x				
Great Tit	x	x	x	x	x	
Greenfinch		x				
Chaffinch	x	x				
Brambling				x	x	
Siskin	x	x		x	x	
Redpoll	x	x		x	x	
Linnet	x	x		x		
Twite				x		
Magpie	x	x		x	x	
Jackdaw		x	x			
Hooded Crow	x	x	x	x	x	x
Raven					x	
Reed Bunting		x	x			
Yellowhammer	x	x	x			
Tree Sparrow	x	x	x			
House Sparrow	x	x	x			
83	32	47	50	32	30	32

List of recorded bird species is based on observations from 1) point censuses; 2) zone mapping and 3) observation from test flight monitoring. Fieldwork: 6 days in June and 3 days in September, 2018.

11 APPENDIX 2 MAP – LISTA TO DENMARK

Location of Lista in perspective of bird migration between Norway and Denmark. Distance between eastern parts of the Lista and Denmark is 150 km; from Lindesnes 130 km and from the Mandal coast only 113 km. Further in the north on the Skagerak coast the distance is about the same; 110 km towards Hirtshals. With a migration speed of 50 km/h, the flight only takes a couple or three hours to pass Skagerak. In stronger wind, i.e. with tailwinds, and perhaps then in higher air strata with greater wind speeds, the crossing would last take only hour or less. Migration corridors are only shown schematically. The migratory direction recorded for several passerines bird species at Lista was in accordance with the lines shown in the map.

